

Meiji University
Graduate School of Governance Studies

Master's Thesis

Housing Management in the Kyrgyz Republic:
No One's Responsibility

Author: Gulnara Kokoeva

June 2013

KOKOEVA GULNARA
MEIJI UNIVERSITY

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ABSTRACT OF THE THESIS

The thesis is devoted to the problem of lack of maintenance of the common property of multifamily buildings. Problem selection was not accidental: the author has often faced with it in everyday life, as well as while working in the local government of the Kyrgyz Republic.

Identification of the factors that adversely affected the implementation of reforms was one of the objectives of the research. Also, it was necessary to identify who and how should maintain the common property, and the obstacles to the implementation of these activities at this time.

The qualitative method has been applied: documentation analysis, comparative analysis and the survey.

The identified factors that had a negative impact on the course of reforms include (1) the lack of consistency of reforms; (2) voluntary formation of the HOA; (3) the lack of a competitive environment among housing managers; (4) inappropriate laws on the activities of the HOA; (5) lack of the awareness of some of the unit owners on the changes that took place during the transition period.

To solve the accumulated problems, numbers of proposals were developed. Their aim is to support and encourage the unit owners (as the co-owners of the common property) to bear the responsibility for the maintenance of the common property.

LETTER OF ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

One of conclusions that I made after the two years of research is that academic profession takes all your time. Despite this, my supervisor Rosario Laratta Sensei, postponing his own studies, was giving me constant support. I owe him my deepest gratitude for his infinite patience and understanding, as well as for leading me through the working process on this thesis.

At the same time, I thank each sensei, especially Aki Yonehara Sensei and Elena Shadrina Sensei, for many hours and valuable advice for my thesis. Also, I share the credit of my work with my colleague Liliana Kuchkacheva and every participant of the survey. Their involvement made a huge contribution to this study.

Finally, I express my appreciation to my son, who in his young age became my friend, adviser and assistant.

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I. INTRODUCTION

“I believe that every right implies a responsibility; every opportunity, an obligation; every possession, a duty”
Rockefeller (1941)

Twenty-two years ago, the Soviet Union collapsed. It has been a long enough period, designed to the transition to a market economy. The transition has been completed in some areas, but this work is devoted to the management of multifamily housing, which is still on the path of retreat from the Soviet system.

The studied problem is common to many countries, but in post-socialist countries it is worth far more acute, weighed down by specific features. Terminology is also rather specific. In this study, “multifamily building” is a condominium, or a building consisting of a number of apartments, owned by different individuals, legal entities and governments. All the multifamily buildings of the Kyrgyz Republic taken together are called “multifamily housing fund”. The term “unit” implies a unit of real estate, i.e., residential apartment or commercial facility (such as hair salons, shops, etc.) located in a multifamily building. As described in detail later, in the Kyrgyz Republic the vast majority of apartments (often in the same building) belong to the citizens of the different social status. With this in mind, the term “unit owners” can be regarded as “citizens” or “people”.

With the exception of the units belonging to the certain unit owners, other parts of a multifamily building are commonly owned by all unit owners in the given building. Common property includes spaces and engineering serving more than one owner: stairs, roofs, exterior walls, basements, piping and so on. The union of apartment owners (or unit owners) formed for the management of common property is called a “homeowners association” (HOA). Housing management is the management of the common property of multifamily buildings, including making decisions on the maintenance of the buildings and the implementation of such

decisions. In turn, maintenance of the common property includes its minor and major refurbishment, cleaning, etc.

In the Soviet Union, most of the multifamily housing fund belonged to the state. Public apartments were rented to citizens on a perpetual lease basis. Since the regime was socialist, the rents were symbolic. The state (as the owner) after a fashion conducted multifamily buildings' maintenance, also for a nominal sum. For about half a century Kyrgyz Soviet citizens lived under such a system.

Since independence, public housing tenants in the Kyrgyz Republic were able to privatize rented housings. The vast majority of tenants took advantage of this opportunity and became full owners of the apartments. The integral parts of multifamily buildings – common spaces and other parts – were supposed to have been commonly owned by the apartment owners. In turn, the property right implies bearing the burden of property maintenance. As with any building, common parts of multifamily buildings require ongoing care.

Nevertheless, the apartment owners have not started taking measures to maintain the common property simultaneously with gaining the title to the apartments. Common property was not the responsibility of the former owner (the state) any more, but the new owners for one reason or another also did not carry the burden of maintenance. In fact, no one has taken the responsibility for the common property. As a result, the condition of the common property of multifamily housing was deteriorating rapidly. Leaking roofs, unkempt staircases, rusty pipes and other consequences became common.

It is obvious that the common spaces are a necessary part of multifamily buildings. A lack of care for the common property will result in the destruction of the entire building. Given the fact that the average salary in the Kyrgyz Republic is equal to the average rents of economy class housing, loss of one's own housing leaves little chance for a decent life. In the Kyrgyz Republic, the share of households living in

multifamily housing is more than 20%, while the share of public housing is less than 1% (National Statistical Committee of the Kyrgyz Republic, 2011). In a lack of public social housing, private (privatized) housing should be considered as social housing.

THE SCOPE AND PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

Finding a way out of the housing management crisis is the main goal of this study. The adoption of timely measures for the maintenance of common property by the stakeholders is seen as the ultimate goal of further reforms. To achieve these goals, it was necessary to identify:

- the factors led to this situation,
- the best management practices in the existing circumstances,
- the gaps between the existing and the desired conditions,
- further steps to be taken to eliminate those gaps.

The methods used for these tasks are described in the next section. The main stakeholders are unit owners, the companies / individual entrepreneurs operating multifamily buildings, and the governments (as the previous owner and due to the social value of multifamily housing).

METHODOLOGY

In order to analyze the current situation and problems in depth, qualitative methods are applied to this research. A comparative study included the legislation and the experiences of other post-socialist countries that are now at different stages of housing reforms. The selected countries are Russia as a country with the housing reforms and legislation similar to the Kyrgyz Republic's one, and Central East Europe countries (CEE) as relatively successful in the implementation of housing reforms.

To study the views of unit owners, the perceptions of the leaders of more than 50 multifamily buildings in the capital city of Bishkek out of 2500 were collected through a survey. The survey was conducted during the 25th of February 2013 to the 5th of May 2013 at the Bishkek mayor's office with the assistance of employees of the Bishkek mayor's office. Among the various visitors to the municipality, building leaders were asked to cooperate for this research. Some questionnaires were filled in through a telephone survey. 56 leaders agreed with filling up the questionnaire, and these were analyzed to understand the leaders' perception. Previously, during the 31st of January to the 1st of February, the pilot survey was carried out with the participation of several leaders of multifamily buildings. The other details of the questionnaire are described in Chapter VI.

Certainly, leaders of the buildings are more conscious of the problem of lack of maintenance of the common property than ordinary unit owners. However, the latter are the key stakeholders, because they are the co-owners of that property. Therefore, the study of unit owners' perception on the issue was particularly important. Because of time and other limitations, a survey of ordinary owners' perception was not feasible. Instead, the excerpts from the relevant groups of the online forums are presented. The groups on the pressing issues are created by the forum participants, and the other participants share their own experiences. Because participants may act anonymously or under a screen name, they express an open mind. This provided an opportunity to understand the real problems faced by unit owners.

Exploring trends in certain periods of the reforms, articles of the online newspapers and other media sources were also actively used. This has helped to note the deterioration or improvement in the situation and to highlight the happenings taking place "right now".

To clarify some points, interviews with several government and municipal officials (the lawyers of the relevant public bodies) were conducted.

Born in the USSR and having spent adult life during a transition period, the author in the study relied on personal experience, including the experience gained while working in the local government of the capital city of the Kyrgyz Republic.

Background of the problem under historical dimension is covered in Chapter II. Chapters III and IV are devoted to Russia and CEE countries respectively. Chapter V focuses directly on the Kyrgyz Republic: its legislation in the field of housing management and the current state of this sector. Chapter VI analyzes the results of the survey. Summarized findings of the study and proposals to address the problems are outlined in Chapter VII.

As stated earlier, the origins of the problem must be sought in the past, to be exact - in the Soviet and the first decade of transition periods, which are described in the next chapter.

II. BACKGROUND OF THE PROBLEM

“The multifamily housing sector in the FSU is like a car stalled on the road to reform”¹

Lipman (2012), p. 1

2.1 HOUSING POLICY DURING THE SOVIET PERIOD

Historically the vast majority of Kyrgyz people were nomadic pastoralists lived in the mountainous areas. Due to this, up to the first half of the 19th century, most of Kyrgyz settlements were nomadic and semi-nomadic types (*ayil*) with portable dwelling (*boz uy*²) (Abramzon, 1990). In the 19th - early 20th century the process of establishing non-nomadic settlements in Kyrgyz began. It intensified after the Russian Revolution of 1917 due to start of the nationalization of land (Kyrgyz had already been annexed by the Russian Empire). The Soviet collectivization³ of agriculture (late 1920s – 1930s) had a huge impact on this process. In the early 1940s the settling of nomadic and semi-nomadic Kyrgyz farms was nearly completed (Dj. Malabayev, *“Kollektivizaciya selskogo hozyaystva i perehod ot kochevnichestva k osedlosti”*).

The collectivization of agriculture, the enlargement of settlements and industrialization led to the emergence of housing shortage problems. Expropriation of existing units and transferring to the working class failed to make a difference. World War II exacerbated the situation (Umurzakova, 2011). The government recognized

¹ FSU – former Soviet Union

² *Boz ui* - portable dwelling of Kyrgyz and other Asian nomads. A frame is set of wooden poles and covered with felt. *Boz uy* is easy to assemble and disassemble, convenient to transport on pack animals. *B.U.* is used by Kyrgyz until now, for example during weddings and funerals, and by pastoralists on summer pastures.

³ Collectivization - process of the abolition of private ownership of the land in favor of the state or (as believed to be) in favor of the collective land ownership. C. was carried out in the shortest time. All property of the peasants, including livestock, was transferred to collective ownership (Underhill et al., 2001).

the seriousness of the problem and tried to take measures to address the housing problem by mass construction of multifamily buildings.

2.1.1 MAIN TYPES OF MULTIFAMILY BUILDINGS

FIRST STAGE: INFILL DEVELOPMENT

Through the end of the 1950s, the Soviet government mainly built two types of multifamily buildings – “*stalinka*” and “*barak*”. The so-called “*stalinka*” (as built during the reign of Stalin⁴), usually two or three storey relatively large and “*blagoustroyennaya*”^{5 6} (“comfortable”) brick buildings consisted of 1-4-room⁷ apartments. Generally, *stalinka* were built for the communist party officials. Some of these buildings are still in good condition. Another type of multifamily buildings was called “*barak*”, one or two storey wooden or brick “*neblagoustroyennaya*” (“uncomfortable”) buildings built for the working class.

However, the construction of these buildings was not enough and could not solve the problem of housing shortage. Many urban residents lived in building basements, unsafe buildings and *baraks*. The situation required fundamental changes in the way of construction.

SECOND STAGE: MASS CONSTRUCTION OF COMPACT APARTMENTS

It was decided to overcome housing crisis by “rationalization, industrialization and low-cost” (Gorlov, 2009). With the adoption of the central government resolutions “On reducing the cost of construction”⁸ in 1950, “On the development of precast concrete structures and components for construction” in 1954, and “On the

⁴ Stalin I. – leader of the Soviet Union from 1920s to 1953.

⁵ Hereinafter all translations are the author’s

⁶ *Blagoustroyennaya* (comfortable) apartment - apartment with hot and cold water supply, toilet and bathroom, *neblagoustroyennaya* (uncomfortable or deplorable) – without listed utilities.

⁷ Typically, in the Kyrgyz Republic number of rooms of apartment includes living rooms and bedrooms; kitchen, restrooms, hallways, balconies, etc. are not taken into account.

⁸ Hereinafter the original titles of the documents are specified in the Table of Authorities (pp. 104-106).

development of housing construction in the USSR” in 1957, the Soviet Union began a massive construction of the panel multifamily buildings.

In the late 1950s, the mass construction throughout the entire territory of the Soviet Union started with the construction of so-called "*khrushchevka*" (as built during the reign of N. Khrushchev⁹). *Khrushchevka* is a 2-5-storey “comfortable” multifamily building with four 1-3 room apartments at each landing. The construction of buildings on the standard design has reduced the time and cost of construction. At present, those multifamily buildings need refurbishment and, therefore, large investment. At the time, such housing was an accomplishment for the Soviet man, and it partly solved the problem of resettlement of citizens in separate apartments. However, the need to build housing in a short time affected the quality of construction works. Housing was built “fast, cheap and a lot” (Gorlov, 2009).

FIGURE II-1: AVAILABILITY OF UTILITIES IN THE APARTMENTS IN THE KYRGYZ REPUBLIC

Source: K. Isayev, “Jilishnoye stroitelstvo”; National Statistical Committee of the Kyrgyz Republic, 2009

THIRD STAGE: MASS BUILDING OF THE “IMPROVED” APARTMENTS

Mass construction of typical multifamily housing continued in the Soviet Union until its collapse, but over the years the types (series) of buildings were

⁹ N. Khrushchev - leader of the Soviet Union from 1953 to 1964

changed to be relatively more comfortable and of higher quality (Figure II-1). In place of "khrushchevka", the urbanized areas of the Kyrgyz Republic was mainly built up of new types¹⁰ of multifamily buildings: the so called "type 104" (1960s - 1970s, 4-5 storey concrete or brick buildings), the "type 105" and the "type 106" (1970s – 1990s, 5-9 storey buildings, 9-storey buildings were equipped with elevators).

The construction was carried out at an accelerated pace. Figures II-2 and II-3 show that in the period of 1971-1985 in the whole USSR public housing construction volumes considerably exceeded all other types (cooperative, personal (private) and *kolkhoz*¹¹) combined. While in the Kyrgyz Republic, public and private housing was built in almost equal amounts, each accounted for almost half of the built-up residential areas.

FIGURE II-2: CONSTRUCTION OF HOUSING BY TYPE OF OWNERSHIP IN THE SOVIET UNION, 1971-1985

Source: "Финансы и статистика" ("Finance and statistics"), 1988 (composed by the author)

¹⁰ In Russian "seriya"

¹¹ Kolkhoz - collective farms in the Soviet Union. In contrast to the state property, which arose as a result of nationalization and confiscation of the means of production, K. farm property was developed from the means of production gathered by peasants on a "voluntary-compulsory" basis. Products produced by state-owned enterprises, was at the disposal of the state, products produced by K. were owned by each K. separately. (G. Aksenok et al, 1950)

2.1.2 DISTRIBUTION OF PUBLIC HOUSING

Being monopolist in the field of multifamily housing, the government in the Soviet Union was its owner, builder, distributor and maintainer. Residents of public dwellings were just tenants. In order to obtain housing, citizens had to place their names on a waiting list at the place of work or with the local authority. Individuals or families whose living conditions did not meet the standards set by the legislation were recognized as *citizens in need of improving living conditions*. The size of provided housing was about 6-8 meters of living space per family member. Housing was provided in turn.

FIGURE II-3: CONSTRUCTION OF HOUSING BY OWNERSHIP IN THE KYRGYZ SOVIET REPUBLIC, 1971-1985

Source: “Финансы и статистика” (“Finance and statistics”), 1988 (composed by the author)

Building a residential house for urban residents was almost impossible because obtaining a land for the construction of detached house in the urban area was extremely difficult. Therefore, citizens had to wait for the state represented by the local government or the state enterprise to provide them with housing. State enterprises built “*vedomstvenniy*” (literally “departmental”) housing for their employees. Municipalities provided housing for other needy citizens registered in the town’s waiting list. Thus, the superior and ordinary worker often resided in the same building.

The buildings usually consisted of apartments of different number of rooms. When determining the size of the housing to be allocated, not only the family size but also the position of the person in need of apartment was taken into account. For example, although people in leadership positions and other people may have had the same number of family members, people in leadership positions tended to get larger apartments.

Typically, it used to take several years, sometimes more than ten years from the registration to allocation of public (departmental) housing. For example, the author's family in the mid-1960s initially rented an accommodation at "*chastniki*" (lit. "individual's", i.e., private property) in the *barak* building. Father had already been registered for several years at his workplace (public enterprise) on the waiting list for housing. He and his young family rented a single room; the hallway and kitchen were shared in common with other family. Several years later, in the late 60's, when my parents were expecting a second child, father's workplace provided them with a one-room apartment. In the late 1970's, with the birth of the fourth child, that is, when the number of family members reached 6 people, father's workplace provided them with a 3-room apartment.

Housing was provided on a perpetual lease basis and thus was considered by the tenant as his/her own. In case of a tenant's death the right to rent was passed to a tenant's family member registered in that apartment. However, the tenants did not have the right to transfer public housing they rented to others¹² except when exchanging it for another public housing. However, finding a suitable dwelling in exchange was problematic. Payment for the difference in the exchange of apartments (e.g., exchange of apartment in the capital to apartment in the suburbs, or a larger one for a smaller one and vice versa) was also illegal and thus was made secretly. When

¹² The right to transfer the good to others – the right to sell, donate or exchange the good

moving to another dwelling, the tenant (and his/her family) had to leave the previous housing to the organization that provided that apartment.

Limitations in transfer of apartments to others were extended even to apartments in cooperative buildings, which were constructed at the expenses of its shareholders (citizens). Cooperative housing has been recognized not as private but as collective property. Thus, apartments in cooperative buildings were owned by a cooperative but not by the individual shareholder. The shareholder could take back his/her share from the housing cooperative, while those who wanted to buy a share also had to buy it from the cooperative's board.

2.1.3 MULTIFAMILY BUILDING MAINTENANCE IN THE SOVIET UNION

In the Soviet Union, expenses for housing and utilities were almost fully covered by the state. The fee for renting the apartment has remained unchanged since 1928; therefore, the fee was a tiny amount and had little impact on the family budget. Utility rates have not changed since 1946, and by the end of 1970-s amounted to about 3-5% of the budget of the workers (Gorlov, 2009).

The state (as the owner of the housing stock) represented by state agencies carried out its maintenance. Direct management was carried out by public housing maintenance organizations¹³ (*JEK*). The tasks of *JEKs* included minor and major refurbishment of buildings, ensuring the smooth operation of the buildings' equipment, maintenance of households in a good sanitary condition, ensuring the careful attitude of tenants to the apartments, as well as improving the living conditions of residents (Bolshaya sovetskaya encyclopediya, 1969-1978).

Refurbishment works carried out by housing maintenance organizations included:

¹³ In Russian “*jilishno-ekspluatatsionnaya kontora*”, “*domoupravleniye*”, etc., abbr. *JEK*, *JEK*, *DU*, etc.

- Refurbishment and replacement of major structures of the multifamily building (foundation, walls, floors, roofs, staircases) and finishing work associated with major refurbishment of the building and apartments.
- Interior refurbishment of residential and common areas (doors, windows, floors).
- Equipping of buildings with plumbing devices, central heating, lifts and other utilities.
- Repair and replacement of apartments' plumbing equipment except their premature failure caused by tenants (Terms of use of units¹⁴, 1962).

Activities of the *JEK* were rather poor. Often criticized by citizens, they were even filmed in a nationwide popular comedy «*Afonya*» (1975). Synopsis by Clarke Fountain describes the view of Western audience on this comedy¹⁵:

“In the former Soviet Union, all apartment blocks were owned by the State. Because they were poorly built and poorly maintained, service and repair people held tremendous power, and used it. One plumber might serve a whole street of apartment buildings, and could demand whatever he wanted in order to perform even the most routine repairs, ie...extra money or a bottle of vodka (or more). In this comedy, the reality of this situation is clearly depicted. Afonya (...) is a typical drunken, bullying plumber, extorting extra money and drink from his victims. He pals around with his buddy Kolya (...), spending most of his "working" day in bars, drinking beer and eating crawfish and salted fish. Despite constant reprimands from the workers' committee, nothing puts a dent in his behavior (...). West Europeans viewing this film found it surrealistic, because they could not believe the situations in it were real. Soviets, on the other hand, found it side-splittingly right on target, and it was very popular.”

Although the situation formed in the Soviet Union's housing sector seems surreal for Europeans, the way of carrying out duties by *JEK* workers described in the movie occurred in reality quite often and even seemed normal. As stated by Rabenhorst (2012), “the political purpose of the state-owned maintenance companies

¹⁴ These Terms were approved by the Council of Ministers of the RSFSR (Russian Federal Republic), but in general, the same rules applied throughout the USSR including the Kyrgyz Republic.

¹⁵ The idea of using this synopsis belongs to Verwalter, 2013.

was to provide employment for workers rather than to provide maintenance services to tenants” (p. 3)

The *JEKs* actively interacted with regional units of the Ministry of Internal Affairs (registration of citizens), the Ministry of Defence (primary account of conscripts) and other state bodies. Thus, the *JEKs* did not only maintain housing fund, but also performed other important public functions. In fact, the *JEK* was a kind of representative of the aforementioned executive authorities.

Resolution “On strengthening the role of house committees in the management of the public housing stock” (1968) shows that Soviet Union began to strengthen the role of house committees (*domovoy komitet*) in the management and conservation of the public housing stock and control of the housing maintenance organizations and tenants. House committees were social formations which were elected by residents of multifamily buildings. The above resolution put on house committees the power:

- to participate in the development of financial plans for housing maintenance organizations and to audit their financial activities,
- to exercise control over the housing maintenance organizations’ expenditure of building materials allocated for the refurbishment of housing,
- and to exercise control over the compliance of rules and standards of technical operation of the housing stock by tenants.

2.1.4 RESPONSIBILITIES OF TENANTS TO RENTED HOUSING AND TO COMMON PROPERTY OF MULTIFAMILY BUILDINGS

Tenants were required to make minor refurbishment of occupied dwellings at their own expense (while major refurbishment, as discussed earlier, had to be carried out by the *JEKs*). Minor refurbishment included:

- whitewashing of ceilings,
- wall painting or wallpapering,

- painting of floors, doors, the inside of the window frames and window sills,
- glazing,
- replacement of windows and door units,
- and repair of wiring from the entrance of the apartment (Terms of use of units, 1962).

According to paragraph 5 of the above Terms, tenants should be warned about the responsibility of all members of his/her family for the maintenance of the apartment, beautification of the land surrounding the building, and about refraining from damaging the common spaces of the building.

Tenants were required to allow *JEK* employees and house committee representatives to enter the dwellings freely and to inspect the technical condition and sanitary maintenance of units. For the violations of the Terms of Use of Units, tenant or persons living with him/her were “subjected to social influence” through the house committees and comrades' courts¹⁶ (ibid).

The Soviet regime, which lasted more than 70 years, shaped a unique mentality of its citizens. From the citizens' point of view, property was divided into two types: public and personal (private). As stressed earlier, rented accommodation, although owned by the state, was seen by citizens as personal property because it was given as a rule in perpetuity. Cases of eviction due to rent non-payment or violation of the terms of use were extremely rare. Property of the state (including common property of multifamily buildings) was considered by citizens as “no one’s” (“*nicheynoye*”) property and was often treated with careless disregard. It is remarkable that in colloquial speech the notion of “public property” was often associated with verb “*rastaskivat*” (figuratively means “to plunder”).

¹⁶ Comrades' courts (*tovarisheskiy sud*) - elected public bodies created in the Soviet Union in order to prevent crime and to impact on people by persuasion and social influence. C.C. examined files on minor offenses (*Yuridicheskaya encyclopedia*, 1984) (Suharev et al. , 1984)

The exceptions were the multifamily buildings of housing cooperatives, because they were originally built by the personal funds of citizens. This explains the caring attitude of its residents to the building and its common property. In addition, only a person with enough financial resources could buy a share in cooperative multifamily buildings, that is, a person of rather high social standing. While the state and departmental housing was given free of charge to any citizen registered on a waiting list, and people of different social status used to live under the same big roof. During survey, one of the chairpersons of the cooperatives (respondent No. 10) indicated as the advantage of this form of management: “*people were initially accustomed to pay for everything*”.

However, as the cooperative housing comprised only a small percentage of the total housing stock, the order prevailing in such buildings could not change the situation as a whole as well as the attitude of the rest of the citizens to the common property of multifamily buildings. On the other hand, the good care of the owners of cooperative housing for the common property of their buildings gives reason to be optimistic.

There were also positive aspects among the tenants of public housing. For example, residents of multifamily buildings used to hold *subbotnik*¹⁷ to clean adjacent territory, usually in the spring and fall. The chairpersons of the multifamily buildings’ house committees used to inform inhabitants about *subbotnik*, and at least one family member from each apartment had to participate in cleaning. At present holding *subbotniks* is still supported by municipalities.

Another good practice was washing of stairs in turn by the residents. Buildings that had three or more apartments on the same landing often used signs “Orderly of

¹⁷ Communist *subbotnik* (lit. “sabbatarian”) – voluntary collective work unpaid for each participant (e.g. cleaning of public areas) on Saturdays or on other time off. *S.* was actually enforced activity. (*Encyclopedicheskiy slovar*, 2009).

Cleaning the Staircase”¹⁸. The residents of the apartment, on whose door hung a sign, washed a staircase from their own floor to the bottom floor for about a week. Then they hung a sign on the next apartment, and thus passed the turn on washing the staircase. Those who were using the staircase could see which of the inhabitants fulfilled his/her social responsibilities.

2.2 POST-SOVIET PERIOD. A DECADE OF HOUSING REFORMS

2.2.1 PRIVATIZATION OF HOUSING AND HOUSING MAINTENANCE ORGANIZATIONS

In 1991, following the collapse of the Soviet Union and subsequent independence, the Kyrgyz Republic began the process of privatization of state property, including the housing stock. In late 1991, the Law “On privatization of housing in the Republic of Kyrgyzstan” was adopted.

The objectives of privatization in all post-Soviet states included (Gentsler, 2010):

- Reduction of subsidies for the maintenance of multifamily housing and putting the burden on property owners;
- Development of the market of housing services and better management of the housing stock.

The right to privatize state housing belonged to the sitting tenants of public apartments. Housing was privatized at a nominal price. Preferential categories of citizens could privatize housing free of charge (for example, families with four and more children, people with disabilities; education, health care, police workers, etc.). Similar laws were adopted in other former Soviet states. In the Kyrgyz Republic, over 90% of public housing was privatized by 1994 (Undeland C., 2002). By 2011 the number reached 93% in the Kyrgyz Republic, 73% in Russia; in Armenia,

¹⁸ In Russian “*Dejurniy po uborke podyezda*”

Kazakhstan and Ukraine privatization of apartments was nearly completed (CIS Statcommittee, 2011). In all former Soviet states mass privatization resulted in “extraordinarily high” rates in homeownership in comparison with the average of 65 percent in Western states (Lipman, 2012) (Figure II-4).

FIGURE II-4: HOUSING STOCK OF PRIVATE AND PUBLIC OWNERSHIP

Source: National Statistical Committee of the Kyrgyz Republic, 2009 (composed by author)

Article 12 of the law on privatization stipulates that maintenance and refurbishment of privatized housing is to be carried out at the expense of its owners. According to Article 13, the owners of apartments in the partially privatized buildings share in the costs of maintenance and refurbishment of technical equipment and common area commensurate with apartment area. Terms of payment and organization of maintenance and refurbishment for the owners of privatized apartments remained the same as for tenants of public housing (paragraph 4 of the Ordinance of Supreme Council of the Republic of Kyrgyzstan “On the Implementation of the Law “On privatization of housing in the Republic of Kyrgyzstan”, 1991).

The above law obliged public housing maintenance organizations to continue maintaining and refurbishing of the buildings under contract with apartment owners, regardless of the number of privatized apartments. In 1997, fifteen housing maintenance departments in Bishkek were combined into one joint-stock company

“*Bishkekzhilremont*”, subdivision of the Bishkek mayor’s office, which had continued to carry out work on the maintenance and refurbishment of the housing stock (Bishkek mayor’s office Resolution “On the establishment of housing refurbishment enterprise “*Bishkekzilremont*”). Organizations responsible for housing maintenance (*JEK*), for emergency refurbishment of plumbing and electrical works, etc. were part of the “*Bishkekzhilremont*”. The functions of the joint-stock company included organization of the activities of the above entities “to ensure the safety, the proper technical operation and maintenance of the housing stock of the city (regardless of ownership), and the implementation of refurbishment and construction, electrical and plumbing work” (ibid).

In 1998, in order to transform housing management sector from the state monopoly to the market form, the central government Resolution “On the concept of the reform of housing and communal services in the Kyrgyz Republic” instructed local authorities to continue further restructuring, de-monopolization and privatization of housing and communal service enterprises (including *JEKs*).

After the *JEKs* were privatized, the state supervision of the quality of their services was not put into force, because the control over the execution of services should be carried out by contractual party, that is, service users (unit owners). Nevertheless, unit owners were not prepared for these changes. Often housing maintenance organizations charged a monthly fee for the maintenance and refurbishment of the common property, but in fact no refurbishment work was carried out. The activities of housing maintenance organizations are elaborated in later chapters.

In 1997, the Kyrgyz Republic Law “On Homeowners Associations” was adopted. It stipulated that HOA is the association of homeowners established for the management of common property of multifamily building. However, the above law

set HOA as a voluntary organization. Norms of the above law and its impact on the problem are to be discussed in detail later.

Gentsler (2010) considers that the main drawback of the privatization of apartments in some of the post-soviet states was that the governments, while initiating the privatization of housing, did not define the responsibility of citizens for the maintenance of common property in multifamily buildings and did not create a mechanism for its management (p. 3). In the Kyrgyz Republic, the law on housing privatization was adopted in 1991, but responsibility for the maintenance of common property was not transferred to the new owners simultaneously. The state remained a monopoly in the housing maintenance sector. The right to joint ownership of the common property in multifamily buildings was established by the Civil Code in 1996. Law on HOAs was adopted in 1997. Maintenance organizations were privatized in the late 1990s - early 2000s.

Stressing the importance of the sequence of reforms (in this case, the lack of sequencing), Stiglitz's (2002) saying relating to reforms in developing countries is notable:

“The market system requires competition and perfect information. But competition is limited and information is far from perfect - and well-functioning competitive markets can't be established overnight. (...) In some cases, reforms in one area, without accompanying reforms in others, may actually make matters worse. This is the issue of sequencing. Ideology ignores these matters; it says simply move as quickly to a market economy as you can. But economic theory and history show how disastrous it can be to ignore sequencing” (p. 74)

Eyk (2005) assumes that mass privatization for “give-away” prices was “short-sighted and a kind of closing one's eyes to a huge problem which cannot be solved automatically”; in the absence of an effective maintenance system, for new owners the maintenance of an apartment rapidly transformed from “too cheap” to “too expensive”. The buildings of similar quality were built in large numbers in the same period. Therefore, problems in these buildings also occur simultaneously in

large numbers, and the measures to address them would require the simultaneous effort of corresponding scale (ibid). Eyk considered multifamily housing stock issues as “one of the most underestimated problem areas”, suggesting to see multifamily housing as social housing with implementation of appropriate public policies.

2.2.2 THE ECONOMIC CRISIS IN THE POST-SOVIET PERIOD AND ITS IMPACT ON THE IMPLEMENTATION OF REFORMS

The housing management problem of post-Soviet countries was also affected by the economic crisis that followed the collapse of the Soviet Union. In the period 1991-1995, the GDP of the Kyrgyz Republic had fallen to 50 percent of its 1990 level. Multifamily buildings are constructed mainly in the cities, thus the studied area is largely applied to urban areas and its residents. The unemployment rate in urban areas was higher than in rural areas: due to the reduction of industry in the period 1991-2004, the unemployment rate in the manufacturing sector (i.e., in urban areas) has increased (International Labour Organization, 2008). Even those with the jobs experienced delays in payment of wages. In the 1990s, delays of payment of wages for several months were common. There has been continued aggravation of poverty (Figure II-5).

FIGURE II-5: POPULATION WITH CONSUMPTION EXPENDITURE BELOW THE POVERTY LINE

Source: National Statistical Committee of the Kyrgyz Republic, 2013 (composed by the author)

Because of the significant reduction in the living standards, citizens did not have sufficient financial resources to pay for the maintenance of the common property of multifamily buildings. In these circumstances, the state could not raise the cost of utility services in proportion to the increase in their cost of production. Economic crisis also had an impact on multifamily building output (Figure II-6).

FIGURE II-6: NUMBER OF BUILDINGS CONSISTING OF MORE THAN ONE DWELLING BY PERIOD OF CONSTRUCTION, KYRGYZ REPUBLIC
Source: National Statistical Committee of the Kyrgyz Republic, 2009 (composed by the author)

Despite the fact that public housing tenants became full owners of dwellings, many of them were not ready to take on the burden of the common property maintenance due to poverty.

2.3 SUMMARY

During the Soviet period, the mass construction of housing including multifamily buildings was conducted in the Kyrgyz Republic. Public multifamily buildings were constructed in a short time and in large quantities. Due to this policy, many people obtained housing. Residents of multifamily buildings were obliged only to take care of the rented apartment and to carry out its refurbishment. The state as the owner of almost all of the multifamily housing heavily subsidized the housing

maintenance sector. Public housing maintenance organizations poorly maintained the common spaces. The situation was worsened by residents' attitudes to the common property as to "no one's" property. Such a system, though faltering, was more or less coping with its tasks.

However, this system had deeply embedded in the mentality of Soviet citizens. Later, it became one of the causes of the studied problem. Citizens were accustomed to the passive role of users of public services in the housing sector.

The situation has changed after the collapse of the Soviet Union. State could no longer maintain multifamily buildings. Firstly, after mass privatization of public housing to the current tenants, the state was no longer the owner of the apartments. Second, due to the economic crisis the state did not have the budget for it.

Since the state could not and should not continue to maintain multifamily buildings, the state should determine the fate of the common property. However, the state formally remained a monopoly in the housing maintenance sector. Public housing maintenance organizations (*JEKs*) were privatized after several years. The quality of the services of the former *JEKs* should have been monitored by the homeowners (as the beneficiaries), that did not happen. As a result, former *JEKs* also ceased to perform their functions.

In turn, new apartment owners were not ready to take on the burden of the common property of multifamily buildings. Apartment owners were not aware that *they* own the common property of the multifamily buildings with all the attendant rights and responsibilities. As the responsibility for a common property has not been determined simultaneously with the privatization, the homeowners considered that the state remains the responsibility. Some of unit owners over the years realized the necessity to bear the costs for the maintenance of common property, but another part still relied on the state. The situation was aggravated by the endemic poverty that followed the economic crisis, which turned the homeowners into "housing poor".

As a result, no one really cared about the common property of multifamily buildings. In turn, it has been leading to deterioration of multifamily buildings. The maintenance system, which was far from perfect in the Soviet era, was destroyed during the several years after gaining independence, while the new system has not been established.

This is the background of the problem of inadequate maintenance of the common property of multifamily buildings in the Kyrgyz Republic. Other post-socialist countries were making different attempts to reform housing management system, which is discussed in the next two chapters.

III. RUSSIAN FEDERATION HOUSING MANAGEMENT REFORM

“The most acute problem of the country today, according to Russians, is housing and communal services”

*Russian Public Opinion Research Center
(2012)*

During the Soviet period and beyond, the housing system of the Russian Federation had similar characteristics as described in the previous chapter. The Russian Federation law “On Homeowners Associations” introduced the institute of homeowners associations in 1996 (one year before the Kyrgyz one). It had established a mechanism allowing unit owners to organize the maintenance of the common property of a multifamily building. At the same time, municipal companies continued to maintain the common property of multifamily buildings.

Despite the adoption of the aforementioned law, a major change for the better has not happened. As cited in the epigraph, considering the situation in the sphere of housing and utility services as the most important problem, concerns of Russians was increasing over time: 52% in October 2011 to 59% in February 2012 (Russian Public Opinion Research Center, 2012). Due to the topical interest of the problem, it was discussed on popular TV programs including the satiric ones:

*“Physics break up the atoms in the collider,
Satellites made the people’s landing on Mars closer.
However, in the staircase number 3 the lamp is off,
For already 20 years the lamp is off. (...)*

*People can build islands, can implant a chip,
Can make cyborgs, and produce in vitro fertilization.
But in the staircase number 3 the lamp is still off,
And everyone is indifferent to my complaints.”* (“Triod i diod” KVN¹⁹ team, 2012)

¹⁹ KVN (“Klub Veselyh i Nahodchivyh”, or “Cheerful’s and Inventive’s Club”) – popular Russian humour TV show.

Problems in the functioning of housing and communal services, deterioration of the housing stock, low quality of maintenance services, and state monopoly with high burden on the state budget led to a fundamental reform of the housing sector (Chekalin, 2006) which began in 2005 with the introduction of the new Housing Code which is the subject of this chapter.

3.1 MULTIFAMILY BUILDING MANAGEMENT METHODS

In Russia, similar to the Kyrgyz legislation, the common property of a multifamily building belongs to the owners of the units in a multifamily building by the right of common ownership (Article 36 of the Russian Federation Housing Code²⁰). The common property includes stairs, elevators, hallways, attics, basements, roofs, building envelope, land plot, electrical, plumbing and other equipment located in the building outside or inside the units and serving more than one unit, etc.

Section VIII of the Housing Code regulates issues of multifamily buildings' management. According to Article 161, the management of the multifamily building should ensure favorable and safe living conditions of residents, proper maintenance of the common property, address issues of usage of said property, and the provision of services to the residents living in that building. The Housing Code obliged unit owners to choose one of the three methods of building management (Table III-1). The following sections discuss in detail each of those three management methods.

General meeting of unit owners was empowered with the right to choose the management method within one year (later these terms were extended). In the case of not meeting deadlines, the relevant local government holds an open tender to select a managing organization. Unit owners are obliged to enter into a building management contract with the managing organization selected by the local government. Before the expiry of the said contract, the local authority convenes a meeting of unit owners in

²⁰ Hereinafter in this chapter all references to the legislation refer to the Housing Code of the Russian Federation, unless otherwise indicated.

that building to address the issue of choosing a building management method, if such a decision had not been made yet by the general meeting of unit owners.

TABLE III-1
METHODS OF MULTIFAMILY BUILDING MANAGEMENT

Management method	Service provider	Service receiver
Direct management of unit owners ²¹ (for buildings consisting of up to 12 apartments)	The person performing the maintenance and refurbishment work and services (e.g. a contractor)	Unit owners
Management by HOA or by housing cooperative	HOA or housing cooperative respectively	
Management by a managing organization ²²	Managing organization	

Source: Housing Code of the Russian Federation, 2004, composed by author

Since the implementation, the housing management reform was often discussed on the web sites of the municipalities and in media. These articles were outlined in the following sections, devoted to each management method.

3.1.1 DIRECT MANAGEMENT OF A BUILDING BY UNIT OWNERS²³

Direct management by unit owners is suitable for small multifamily buildings, thus it can be chosen for the buildings consisting of up to 12 apartments. Due to the small number of units, it is relatively easy to assemble its owners to conduct a general meeting (Table III-2). Usually the neighbors in such buildings know each other well and achieving agreement among them is not as difficult as in the more common larger buildings. Homeowners in the buildings consisting of more than four apartments have to choose a multifamily building council from among unit owners (to be described later).

²¹ In Russian “*neposredstvennoye upravleniye*”

²² In Russian “*upravlyayushaya organizatsiya*”

²³ This section is heavily based on the article of Djus, 2012₂ and “Nonprofit Partnership of Enterprises of Housing Complex” (“MejRegionRazvitiye”)

TABLE III-2
ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF THE DIRECT CONTROL METHOD

Advantages	Disadvantages
Building management	
Independence from managing organization or from HOA/housing cooperative.	No professional manager who would defend the interests of a multifamily building on a permanent basis.
Finance issues	
Reduced cost of building maintenance due to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • absence of administrative apparatus, • part of maintenance works can be performed by owners themselves, and • no need to pay for free-riders, as each unit owner pays directly to a utility company or to a contractor but not to the general account of the building as in other management methods (free-riding problem is described later). 	Ineligibility of inclusion into the regional target program for the major refurbishment of multifamily buildings (state Housing Reform Fund ²⁴) and, therefore, ineligibility to receive the relevant state budget funds. The right to be included in this program is possessed by HOAs, housing cooperatives and management organizations (i.e., by legal entities). No savings fund, which entails the need to collect large financial contributions for major repairs.

Source: Djus, 2012, “*MejRegionRazvitiye*”, compiled by author

Positive aspects of the direct control method mainly consist of the low financial cost of unit owners in comparison with other management methods. Those aspects seem temporary in nature. Deterioration of the building due to lack of proper maintenance seems inevitable. Being interested in the preservation and maintenance of their habitation, unit owners should eventually choose a more efficient management method.

Typically, multifamily buildings in Russia consist of more than 12 apartments. Therefore, most of the multifamily buildings hire a managing organization and / or form an HOA.

3.1.2 BUILDING MANAGEMENT BY HOMEOWNERS ASSOCIATION

According to the Housing Code, HOA is the *union* of unit owners in a multifamily building formed for the joint management of common property. HOA is

²⁴ In Russian “*Fond sodeystviya reformirovaniyu JKH*”

a legal entity. The following are the requirements of the Housing Code on the operation of HOAs. Positive or negative impacts of these rules are set out in Table III-3.

OPERATION OF THE HOAS

Formation of an HOA requires the consent of more than 50% of votes of unit owners. Decision to establish an HOA is taken at the general meeting of unit owners (Art. 136).

Membership of unit owners in HOA is voluntary, in contrast to the practice in most countries of the world. An obstacle to mandatory membership in HOA was Article 30 of the Constitution of the Russian Federation, which states, “no one can be compelled to join any *union* or to remain in it”. In 1998, the decision of the Constitutional Court of the Russian Federation declared as invalid the provisions of the mandatory membership in HOA determined by the Law on HOAs (1996). Most likely, this circumstance was also the cause of the establishment of several management methods rather than a single method mandatory for all buildings. The following chapters ground that the lack of the requirement for mandatory formation of the HOAs is one of the main causes of the studied problem.

An HOA can conduct maintenance and refurbishment of the common property by themselves or through engaging third parties and controlling the quality of services and works. Funds and property of HOA consist of compulsory payments of HOA members, state subsidies, and revenue from business activities of the HOA (Art. 151). Permitted business activities of HOA include maintenance and refurbishment of real property in the multifamily building, construction of additional facilities and common property in the building, and renting out of the common property (Art. 152).

Management of an HOA is carried out by its Board elected by the general meeting from among the members of the HOA. In turn, the Board elects the chairperson of the HOA from among the Board’s members. Thus, only a member of

HOA, that is the owner of the unit in the multifamily building, can be a chairperson of HOA or a member of the Board.

TABLE III-3
ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF HOA MANAGEMENT METHOD

Advantages	Disadvantages
HOA management	
<p>Possibility for unit owners to participate in the management of common property.</p> <p>High efficiency due to high interest of HOA members.</p> <p>Better coordination and administering due to existence of the leaders – the Board of the HOA.</p>	<p>As only a unit owner can be an HOA Chairman, the effectiveness and even existence of HOA often depends on whether there is a reasonably competent unit owner ready to take on this job.</p> <p>Potential wrongful acts of HOA’s executives.</p>
HOA finance	
<p>Possibility to carry on business activity and to generate income within the HOA.</p> <p>Possibility for unit owners to check the use of HOA finances.</p> <p>Opportunity to receive government exemptions and subsidies for major refurbishment.</p> <p>Opportunity to establish the size of tariff (payments).</p> <p>Conditions for economical use of water, heat, etc. by installation of metering devices</p> <p>As a consequence of proper management, increase of the market value of apartments, as well as reduce of the cost of maintenance</p>	<p>Probability of HOA’s bankruptcy due to misallocation of resources, unprofessional management, etc.</p> <p>Uncertainty of the sources of funds for major refurbishment.</p> <p>Free-riders and the absence of leverage on them.</p> <p>Inverse relationship of the building’s size and maintenance expenditures (divided among every unit).</p>
Social issues	
<p>Improving relations between inhabitants: through participation in general meetings, neighbors get to know each other and learn to work together for the common interest.</p> <p>Employment of inhabitants who have a tendency for social work or who want to have a part time job close to his/her home</p>	<p>Low participation of unit owners in the process of establishment of HOA and its subsequent activities.</p> <p>Difficultness of taking into account views of all HOA members and as a consequence emergence of conflicts.</p>

Greater effectiveness of the collective power in the improvement of the multifamily building's condition and in the protection of the building's common property.	
Enabling respect for the common areas, as inhabitants know that they have to pay for refurbishment.	
HOAs and the government	
Higher effectiveness of raising the profile of HOA's appeals to public and other agencies.	

Source: Compiled by author from Aphanasiy (2009) and Informational Resource Center for Khabarovsk city.

Vihavainen (2009) notes that most of the HOAs in Russia were formed due to the state reform, but not by the initiative of residents. Excessive pressure of authorities to increase the number of generated HOAs led to the establishment of formal, non-working HOAs. On the other hand, Vihavainen found that residents of the buildings managed by HOAs began to treat the common property of their multifamily buildings more carefully so that its condition has improved.

Borisova (2011) identifies external factors that influence the efficiency of HOAs. Negatively influencing factors include the age of the building, inequality [*economic inequality of inhabitants – G.K.*] and presence of a managing organization. Positively influencing factors are large size of HOA, social capital (affects the activity of HOA and its Board), large share of private units and formation of HOA on the initiative of residents.

Here it is worth to recall one quite significant difference between the situation in Russia and the Kyrgyz Republic, mentioned in Chapter II. By 2011, in Russia 73% of public housing stock was privatized compared with to 93% in the Kyrgyz Republic. Therefore, in Russia there are still many public units under the same roof with privatized ones. The aforementioned experts say that it may hinder the activities of the HOA because the state is unlikely to be actively involved in those activities.

Analysis of the role of HOAs in the housing management reform of the post-socialist countries is continued in the following chapters.

3.1.2-1 BUILDING MANAGEMENT BY HOUSING COOPERATIVE

As described in the previous chapter, a housing cooperative is formed in order to meet the needs of citizens in housing, and involves its members' funds (contributions) in the construction, renovation and subsequent maintenance of a multifamily building (Section 5 of the Housing Code). The supreme governing body of the housing cooperative is the general meeting of members of the cooperative. A member of a housing cooperative obtains an apartment in the multifamily building of the housing cooperative in accordance with the amount of contribution. The basis to obtain the dwelling is a decision of a general meeting of the cooperative.

Thus, the members of the housing cooperative build a house at their own expense rather than obtain it from the state. Generally, cooperatives' members deliberately bear the rights and responsibilities for the building from the beginning of its construction, including the responsibility for the common spaces of multifamily building.

3.1.3 BUILDING MANAGEMENT BY A MANAGING ORGANIZATION

According to the Housing Code, a managing organization is a legal entity carrying out the management of a multifamily building. In contrast to HOA, managing organizations are for-profit companies. A managing organization is responsible for unit owners for the provision of *all* common property maintenance services and work. Presumably, the legislator, emphasizing the responsibility of the managing organization for *all* the services and work, took into account the fact that those companies often try to limit their duties to the minimum (as shown in Chapter V by the example of the former *JEKs* of the Kyrgyz Republic).

The Housing Code stipulates that after a certain period when unit owners can choose the management method, the local authority selects a managing organization with which unit owners have to sign a contract. According to the amendments made to the Housing Code in 2011, if later unit owners appeal regarding the non-compliance of contract terms by a managing organization, a local authority conducts an unscheduled audit of the latter (Art. 165). Most likely, these amendments were made due to the frequent violations of the managing organizations, described later. In case of the confirmation of a breach of the contract, the local authority convenes a meeting of unit owners to deal with the termination of the contract with the managing organization and selecting a new managing organization, or changing the building management method (ibid). However, one should take into account that if the managing organization had been selected by the municipality, there can be a conflict of interest for the latter.

DIFFICULTIES OF MANAGING ORGANIZATIONS

Main challenges of managing organizations:

- 1) Free-riding. Managing organizations face difficulties collecting payments from inhabitants for provided utility and maintenance goods and services. When entering into supply contracts with utility companies, the managing organization acts on behalf of all unit owners of the maintained multifamily building. Therefore, the managing organizations are required to pay for all residents including those who delay or refuse to pay.
- 2) The probability of unfair competition due to biased tenders. It is often discussed in the media that the local governments carry out biased competitive selections of managing organizations, which can negatively affect their activities and their image as a whole.

CASES OF VIOLATIONS BY MANAGING ORGANIZATIONS

As the managing organizations are responsible for all services and works including provision of utility services, the payments for a latter first go to the general account, and then are transferred to the utility companies. Subsequently, the most frequent violations discussed in the media include:

- Embezzlement or misappropriation of funds received from unit owners for utility products and services. The subsequent large debts on these payments can lead to the bankruptcy of the company.
- Deliberate bankruptcy. In this case, unit owners are likely to litigate to confirm payments for delivered utilities.
- Payments overestimation (when billing for provided utilities and for the maintenance of a building).

For clarity, below is a brief overview of some online news of the first week of February 2013:

- Penza city. One of the managing organizations used excessive rates when billing for heating. As a result, residents of the multifamily buildings were excessively charged on more than 2 million Russian rubles [*more than 65000 USD – G.K.*] ("Penzenskaya Pravda" , 2013).
- Chuvash Republic. One of the managing organizations failed to pay in full to a utility supplier for the actual delivered heat energy. Furthermore, the head of the managing organization abducted the funds in the amount of approximately 58 million Russian rubles received from heat consumers (i.e., unit owners), and embezzled legal service's and energy audit service's funds of more than 21 million rubles (Ministry of the Interior of Russian Federation, 2013).
- Voronezh city. Six managing organizations declared bankrupt within a month. The total amount of debts to utility suppliers exceeded 1.1 billion rubles. The

article says that, according to the lawyer, “All frauds [*by deliberate bankruptcy – G.K.*] were carried out to obtain benefits” (mail.ru, 2013).

Currently, some local governments and state agencies publish the lists of managing organizations that had the largest number of violations in the operation and maintenance of the housing stock, or received many complaints.

As grave violations are financial ones, the managing organizations’ activities call for increase of their responsibility and financial security. Mandatory insurance of managing organizations and expansion of their authorized fund can prevent homeowners from unwanted consequences of companies’ bankruptcy. Enhancing their transparency requirements can reduce cases of over-rates and other financial irregularities.

Due to the complexity of establishment and operation of an HOA, managing organizations seem to be an essential element in the housing management sphere. Like any new endeavor, the institute of managing organizations is currently on the difficult path of establishment and development.

3.1.4 MULTIFAMILY BUILDING COUNCIL

According to the amendments to the Housing Code, adopted in 2011 (Art. 161.1), in multifamily buildings consisting of more than four apartments but not having formed an HOA or cooperative, a multifamily building council²⁵ must be elected. A multifamily building council (hereinafter in this chapter a “building council”) is elected at the general meeting from among unit owners. A chairperson of the building council, based on power of attorney issued by unit owners, concludes a contract with the managing organization, controls performed works and services by a contractor or a managing organization and carries out other administrative functions. In fact, a building council is an analogue of the HOA, with one difference - building

²⁵ In Russian “*sovet mnogokvartirnogo doma*”

council is not subject to state registration. That is, a building council is not a legal entity with all the consequences (e.g., a building council does not have to pass the tax reporting, but on the other hand, it has no access to state grants and subsidies).

If the decision to elect a building council was not made or such a decision was not implemented within one year, the local authority during three months convenes a general meeting of unit owners, in order to elect a Council and its chairperson, or to establish an HOA. Thus, after the 2011 amendments, unit owners have to choose one of two management methods. The first option: unit owners can form an HOA, which in turn can operate independently or can hire a managing organization. The second option (in case of rejection to form HOA): to elect a building council, though a building council is not considered as a building management method. If the number of apartments exceeds 20, unit owners after electing a building council have to hire a managing organization. Almost certainly, the decision to establish the institute of a building council had been dictated by necessity for each building to have its representative body consisting of the unit owners, while establishing mandatory formation of an HOA was impossible.

3.2 SUMMARY

Certainly, the problems accumulated over decades in the field of housing management cannot be solved overnight. However, since the start of the 2005 reform, legislation on housing management is gradually improving and market of managing organizations is developing. Probably, there is a need to continue to raise the awareness among citizens on the management of common property. The effectiveness of HOAs can rise significantly when strengthening its capacity and determination of its mechanism of leverage on free riders.

The establishment of several management methods (including management by private for-profit organizations) instead of selecting one, but the same for all

buildings, seems to be a forced measure because of the contradictions of mandatory membership of unit owners in HOA to the Russian Constitution. The subsequent decision on reduction to two methods - building council and HOA (excluding private for-profit organization as an independent management method) - confirms the need for each building in the current environment for a single managing body consisting of the unit owners.

Exclusion of private for-profit organizations as an independent management method is a consequence of the facts of serious financial irregularities. This leads to the conclusion that in the current embryonic state of the housing market, financial means of residents should not be entrusted to private companies. This function should be implemented by the unit owners through its single representative body. Again, the bad practice of some managing companies proves the need for an HOA in each building, even if the building is managed by a professional private manager.

Empowering local governments to conduct contests to choose managing organizations was, perhaps, a necessary decision related to the low activity of unit owners - a trait common to Soviet citizens. As described in Chapters V-VI, this problem is also typical in the Kyrgyz Republic. Without this measure, it would be difficult to “break the deadlock” and to solve the problem of selecting the management method. However, experts say the low preparedness of public authorities for the housing reform and lack of responsibility of local authorities for the selection of unscrupulous managing organizations. If Kyrgyz legislators adopt similar rules (which is expected), they should provide preventive measures against these problems.

Many of housing management problems is inherent in both Russian Federation and the Kyrgyz Republic. Given the fact that the legislation of the Kyrgyz Republic often takes the example of Russian legislation, taking into account the experience of the latter can be extremely valuable for the Kyrgyz Republic. At the

same time, it is also worth to examine the experience of other countries, especially those relatively successfully implemented housing reforms.

IV. HOUSING MANAGEMENT REFORM IN HUNGARY AND OTHER CEE COUNTRIES

Central Eastern Europe countries (CEE) since the end of World War II and until the early 1990s were under the influence of the Soviet Union, having had housing policies similar to the latter: the vast majority of multifamily housing was owned, maintained and subsidized by the state. However, after the fall of the regime, the regions moved on different paths. While many post-Soviet countries have been in a closed circle, introducing reforms similar to each other, the countries of CEE due to the proximity of the European Union (EU) learned from their more developed neighbors. This chapter summarizes the experience of CEE countries (with a more detailed study of the Hungarian practice as one of the most successful) and makes a comparison with Western Europe.

4.1 HOUSING REFORMS IN CEE ²⁶

In the early 1990s in the CEE, as in the USSR, poorly constructed and maintained housings were passed into the ownership of sitting tenants for a small amount or free of charge. Nevertheless, unlike the post-Soviet states, CEE countries simultaneously with the privatization established the responsibility of unit owners for common property by transferring joint ownership of common property along with the ownership of the units.

However, housing reforms in each CEE country have their own characteristics, especially in terms of the formation of HOA. In Hungary, the establishment of an HOA is mandatory for each multifamily building. In Slovakia, unit owners can choose between forming the HOA and / or hiring a manager. In Romania, though the formation of HOA is mandatory, this requirement is not sufficiently fulfilled because the law does not set penalties for non-compliance. Due to these differences, the

²⁶ This section is heavily based on publication of Rabenhorst (2012)

reform implementation among CEE countries and its consequences also varied. It is important to identify the factors led to a positive outcome, when each of the stakeholders was acting in good faith on the maintenance of common property.

Rabenhorst (2012) identifies *proper legal framework* and its fulfillment as the primary basis for the management of the common property. Legislation should reflect at least next rules (ibid):

- Registration of the unit and respective share in the common property in the land cadastre. This is necessary to determine the proportion of payments for maintenance costs and to obtain loans for refurbishments;
- Registration of HOAs as legal entities in order to represent the interests of all owners when concluding contracts and to protect the rights of HOA to third parties; government support of the registration process;
- Mandatory formation of HOA and compliance with this requirement;
- The availability of adequate powers of HOA to ensure obligations of unit owners including payments for common property maintenance.

Another important factor is the effectiveness of the program of privatization of public housing maintenance organizations as they tend to use their funds inefficiently (Gentsler, 2010). The countries that have retained the system of state monopoly on housing maintenance have fewer funds for the building maintenance because of the high cost of bloated number of staff of public organizations. In addition, monopoly service providers have no incentive to develop and to improve their services (ibid).

The experience of CEE countries shows that reforms accompanied by requirements or strong recommendations to form HOAs were the most successful. Without a well-drafted law on HOAs and subsequent formation of an HOA, there is no effective system of managing the common areas and enforcing rules and obligations imposed on the apartment owners:

“Without HOAs, owners almost never engage in major renovations or even substantial improvements to their buildings because they lack a framework for planning, financing, and implementing work on that scale” (Rabenhorst, 2012, p.1)

In those CEE countries, where HOAs was not mandatory or this requirement was not fulfilled, the percentage of multifamily buildings with HOA was quite low, while conditions of buildings without HOA were relatively poor.

Gentsler (2010) assumes that association of unit owners in the form of a legal entity (to make joint decisions) hiring a professional manager (to implement joint decisions of the unit owners) is the best practice of multifamily building management. In this type of management, decisions are made on a democratic basis and management services meet the needs and capabilities of the unit owners.

4.1.1 HUNGARY’S EXPERIENCE

Experts identify Hungary as an example of the successful implementation of the housing management reform. The latter included a package of measures outlined in this section.

While in many post-socialist countries, including the Kyrgyz Republic, a detailed determination of unit owners’ responsibility for the common property was carried out several years after the beginning of mass privatization, Hungary has taken timely and appropriate legislative solutions, such as establishment of HOA as a condition of privatization of the first apartment in the building, and other important decisions:

“A big advantage in Hungary compared to many other post-socialist countries (e.g. Slovakia, Romania, Bulgaria, Albania), was that the Law on Condominiums successfully regulated the transfer of property and the establishment of the new institutional structure (the assembly, the election of condominium manager, the decision-making procedures, the condominium fee). Where such a law did not exist and the relations between the new owners of the privatised multi-family buildings remained unclarified, maintenance of common parts of buildings was virtually non-existent” (Hegedüs and Teller, 2005, cited by International Finance Corporation (2011), p. 77)

The Hungarian Government has taken decisive steps to encourage the formation of HOAs. One of the most important solutions was granting authority to HOAs to impose a lien on the property of the unit owner who is delaying payment of his/her share of the maintenance cost. This decision can be made with the consent of the general meeting. After the sale of the property, HOA can foreclose the debt through the court (International Finance Corporation, 2011). The obligation of utility providing organizations to install metering devices for each multifamily building also contributed to the improvement of the efficiency of HOAs (New Eurasia Foundation).

Legislative changes in 2004 made it possible for HOAs to make decisions by simple majority, including issues on obtaining loans and on increase in overall costs (except for the “expenditures which exceed the range of ordinary management expenditure”, e.g. construction of a new building) (International Finance Corporation, 2011). These amendments has led to an increase in cases of reconstruction of multifamily buildings.

A system of budgetary grants is allocated for the refurbishment of the common property by at least 60% co-payment on the part of HOAs. In addition, municipalities within the social assistance programs provide funds to pay off the debt of disadvantaged families for housing maintenance and utilities (New Eurasia Foundation).

Municipalities regularly provide consultative support to HOAs, holding monthly meetings of the club of chairpersons of HOAs and housing cooperatives. The purpose of those meetings is to exchange the experiences and the information on new legislation, and to give the participants opportunity to meet representatives of municipalities and utility providers. In addition, free legal and other counseling is held on a weekly basis. Information regarding the HOAs is also placed in the municipal media, and legislative series and guidelines are published and distributed free of charge (New Eurasia Foundation).

Thus, the success of the Hungarian housing reforms is due to (1) setting strict and timely requirements on the mandatory formation of HOAs, (2) improving the effectiveness and efficiency of HOAs through simplification of its decision-making process and development of a mechanism of debt recovery, and (3) providing regular information and institutional support of HOAs and cooperatives.

However, it should be recognized that there are also differences in the background of Hungary's multifamily housing. Unlike former Soviet Union states (FSU) where the entire apartment stock belonged to the state, in Hungary during the socialist period private ownership of units in multifamily buildings had not ceased to exist (Rabenhorst, 2012). The same can be said about the legislation on HOAs: it already existed in Soviet times. Therefore, citizens were familiar with this type of ownership and its rights and responsibilities, which gave great advantages in carrying out housing reforms (ibid).

Currently HOAs consisting of more than six units are managed either by HOA itself or by private or municipal companies (International Finance Corporation, 2011). A highly developed market of multifamily building managers (Figure IV-7) is the result of effective reforms, in particular the legislative decision on the formation of HOA in each building.

4.2 DISTINCTIONS OF HOUSING MANAGEMENT IN THE WESTERN EUROPE AND THE POST-SOCIALIST COUNTRIES²⁷

A comparison of the housing management sector in the post-socialist and traditionally capitalist countries is quite difficult, because the historical, political, economic and cultural sides are rather different. At the same time, giving a brief overview of the West's experience still worth it, in order to understand the similarities and the differences.

²⁷ This section is heavily based on the presentation by Eyk (2005)

Source: Rabenhorst, 2012 (composed by author)

FIGURE IV-7: MULTIFAMILY BUILDINGS MANAGEMENT IN HUNGARY

As in the post-soviet states, in Europe multifamily buildings were built on a relatively mass basis from the 1960s to the 1980s. HOAs were not so extended, because most of the buildings were entirely in the public or in the private property (owned by one owner). Share of an apartment fund in the total housing stock also differs: while in the post-socialist countries and the former Soviet Union, due to previously discussed communist housing policy, the apartment fund represents a significant part; in Western Europe, it makes for a much smaller proportion.

The process of demolition of multifamily buildings takes place in some countries in Western Europe due to the high financial status of their HOAs. For CEE and FSU, demolition seems rather expensive; instead, it is worth more to invest in the renovation of existing housing stock.

Eyk's (2005) remarks on the legal framework of HOAs in a European context include:

- Compulsory membership in HOAs for all unit owners
- Registration of HOAs as legal entities, and
- A minimum quorum for HOA's decision-making

As is evident, most of these requirements have been met by some CEE countries from the beginning of housing reforms. While in the Kyrgyz Republic, as shown later, these standards were either adopted with a significant time lag, or not adopted so far.

Discussing problems faced by HOAs in post-regime countries, it should be noted that the HOAs in the West also face some similar difficulties. Typically, problems occur when raising funds for the major refurbishment of the building. Eyk (2005) also mentioned about “dormant” HOAs in Rotterdam, which cannot afford serious maintenance activities because their buildings are of poor quality, and thus inhabited by the disadvantaged. In the Kyrgyz Republic, this problem has become rather significant due to the high level of poverty. This seems like a vicious circle. The poor can afford only neglected low-cost housing. Then, they cannot afford the proper maintenance of housing. In turn, it leads to further deterioration of the buildings. In this circumstances, the suggestion of Eyk to countries in transition to consider privatized housing as social housing is particularly important.

After comparing the situation with Europe, it becomes clear why the problem of housing management is so severe in the post-socialist countries, while in traditional capitalist countries the issue is not as acute. There are differences in the proportion of multifamily housing. At the same time, in Europe low quality of the buildings and unit owners’ neglect to the common property are not scale problems.

4.3 SUMMARY

Despite common communist past and, therefore, with similar housing problems, during a period of reforms CEE promptly shifted to a market economy, including the housing maintenance sector. Certainly, the situation was alleviated by the fact that CEE post-socialist states were not as “regime” states as the Soviet Union:

“Because the countries of NIS [Newly Independent States – G.K.] were governed by a communist regime for a longer period of time than those of CEE, housing is in an even more deteriorated condition, and there is little trust among neighbors or between citizens and the government to foster the cooperation needed to make large-scale projects possible. Technical, social, and financial conditions all make the situation for privatized housing in NIS very dire indeed” (Rabenhorst (2012), p. 13

However, it should be recognized that the success of the CEE reform is primarily due to adequate legislative decisions (although other factors such as relatively sustainable economic growth also had its impact).

There is no such a great variety in the methods of housing management, as in Russia and in the Kyrgyz Republic. The only management method is the HOA, but it is compulsory for all buildings. This is the main lesson to learn. At the same time, steps should be taken to ensure compliance with this provision. In turn, HOA can either independently manage the building or hire a professional manager. Another important factor, closely related to the previous one, was the development of the market of housing managers.

Learning from the experience of establishing a minimum quorum in a voting process seems necessary in the light of the low participation of unit owners often discussed in the Kyrgyz Republic. Strengthening the powers of HOAs made their job more effective and efficient. As previously described, the free-riding problem is one of the most acute issues in Russia, even after the 2005 reform. The same is true in the Kyrgyz Republic. The absence of effective leverage on defaulters restricts the activities of the HOA, denying it of funds for actually executed or planned work. However, the imposition of pledge and subsequent sale of the housing (in contrast to the Soviet practice of “no eviction”) seems harsh. Development of instruments adapted to the conditions of the Kyrgyz Republic should be the way out.

HOAs support practice through the provision of municipality budget grants for refurbishment and through information support, carried out in Hungary, takes place in Bishkek too. One section of the next chapter is dedicated to those initiatives

of the Bishkek local government. However, as shown by the example of CEE, without a strong legal framework at the national level, the necessary results cannot be achieved.

As emphasized earlier, the requirement of the compulsory formation of HOA in each building before privatization of the first apartment was the key decision for successful practices. Because most of the apartments in the Kyrgyz Republic have already been privatized, it is too late to implement this practice. The search for alternative solutions to overcome this situation is one of the purposes of this study.

V. THE CURRENT STATE OF THE HOUSING MANAGEMENT IN THE KYRGYZ REPUBLIC

“A huge gap took place between the economic reforms of the country, the process of housing privatization, its management, and citizens’ psychology”
Timirbayev (2006)

“There have been some refurbishment activities inside dwellings, but almost nothing has been done to deal with the common parts of the buildings.”
UNECE²⁸ (2010), p.5

Leaking roofs, broken elevators, damp basements, unkempt staircases and courtyards – after the collapse of the Soviet Union including its housing maintenance system, all this has become commonplace for residents of most of the multifamily buildings in the Kyrgyz Republic. Some of the reasons led to such a state have been described in the earlier chapters.

It would be wrong to say that the government did not carry out reforms in this sector. Reforms took place, but why have they not proven effective enough? In order to answer this question, this chapter examines the status of the multifamily building management sector and identifies the differences from the relatively successful countries. The goal is to analyze the current state of housing management sector, the impact of reforms to the current situation, and to make a comparison with the practice of the more successful countries in order to determine further steps that can help to address the mounting problems.

According to the census in 2009, the urban population of the Kyrgyz Republic is almost 30%, and nearly half of the urban population resides in the capital city of Bishkek. With this in mind, this chapter focuses on the situation in Bishkek.

²⁸ United Nations Economic Commission for Europe

5.1 BUILDING MANAGEMENT METHODS

In the Kyrgyz Republic, the issues of management of the common property in multifamily buildings are regulated by the Civil Code, 1996 and the Law “On the Homeowners Associations”, 1997 (hereinafter “the Law”).

In accordance with the amendments to the Law introduced in 2002 (Art. 18-1), homeowners (75% of those present at the general meeting) are free to choose the method to manage the common property from among following:

- Direct control of homeowners (in case the building consists of up to four units);
- An HOA;
- Authorized manager (an individual or organization) or local government organization;
- Other methods stipulated by the legislation.

As can be seen, management methods are similar to the provisions of the Russian Housing Code 2005. One of the key differences is that in Russia a management method must be chosen for each multifamily building, while in the Kyrgyz Republic selection of a management method is not obligatory. This situation often leads to the absence of any management whatsoever. However, a draft Housing Code, which is currently under consideration, also provides for mandatory selection of management method (to be described later).

In fact, existing management methods include management by former *JEKs* (*domoupravleniye*), by cooperative and by HOA. House Committee cannot be considered as the common property management method, as management is not part of its duties (Bishkek Council (*Kenesh*) resolution “On city block and housing committees”, 2011). The following describes the activities of former *JEKs* and HOAs.

5.2 CURRENT ACTIVITIES OF BISHKEK MAINTENANCE ORGANIZATIONS

Public maintenance organizations' activities in the Soviet period and their transformation into private ownership (usually limited liability companies, thus colloquially called "OsOO" (an equivalent of LLC) was described in Chapter II. The housing system was characterized by the omnipotence of the state maintenance organizations and by the low quality of their services. The situation was weighed down by citizens' attitude to common property of multifamily buildings as to "no one's" property, while the government paid "for everything" and citizens were just receiving it almost free of charge. After public maintenance organizations were privatized, the service users (i.e., unit owners) were supposed to carry out supervision of the quality of their services. However, former *JEKs* mainly continued to operate in the same way (currently former *JEKs* maintain about 30% of the Bishkek multifamily buildings). This situation raises two important questions. Why did the reforms in the housing maintenance sphere not positively affect their activities? Why did the citizens not demand better quality, when they became apartment owners, and maintenance organizations became private?

One of the reasons is that the reforms were not simultaneous. Housing was privatized in the early 1990s, but the state remained a monopoly in the housing maintenance sector. The law on HOAs was adopted in 1997. Maintenance organizations were privatized about 10 years after housing privatization started: in the late 1990s - early 2000s. Study of ordinary unit owners' perception expressed on the online forums revealed their unawareness on the changes taking place in the housing management sector. Some of the unit owners even did not know that maintenance organizations were privatized:

"Is it true that domoupravleniye [building maintenance organizations – G.K.] are not state or municipal organizations? So for what do they regularly send bills? We collect the money for all of the problems in the building by ourselves (...). They extort money! They do nothing!" (Lizbett, 2007)

Moreover, the service organizations have successfully used the unawareness of unit owners. The quality of their services has not changed, but rather, as evidenced by the numerous comments in the media, it was often reduced to almost zero:

“It turned out that we do not have a contract with the domoupravleniye. However, they regularly, every month, send us the bills for the work not performed. And we regularly pay them” (Lizbett, 2007)

“We [unit owners – G.K.] pay for cleaning of the staircase by ourselves, we have installed an intercom by ourselves, but the LLC sends the bills every month. What do we have to pay for? The neighboring buildings’ inhabitants wrote a statement [to the LLC about refusing their services –G.K.] and they stopped sending bills” (Urmatoff, 2012)

“What kinds of bills come every month for 90 som²⁹ for the maintenance of the common areas? Nothing changes in the staircase . We change the lamps by ourselves, nobody else ever changed them. The plaster coat fell off, dirty staircases. What should I pay for?” (Igloo, 2012)

“Don’t pay them anything. Our building is also sort of “maintained” by them. They think that we are going to pay them as if through inertia (...). No one has ever seen them in our district.” (sledovatel, 2012)

“You need to inform them in writing to terminate the contract, but they do not sign these statements (...). Therefore, we had to go to court to terminate the contract, as they have not fulfilled their obligations as intermediaries [between unit owners and the contractors – G.K.]. (...) We won the case! It turns out that there is no contract, because they [the LLC – G.K.] prolong them after expiration (1 year) unilaterally! (...) It is easier to hire someone by ourselves, but not to pay for the missing work + for their staff!” (pozitiff, 2007)

As one of the online forum participants said, despite a lack of any building maintenance work, many residents continue to pay bills of former *JEKs* as if through inertia. The roots of this situation should be sought in the absence of widespread explanation on the ongoing reform, such as the unit owners’ rights and responsibilities with respect to the common property, a change of *JEKs*’ ownership and the implications thereof.

²⁹ Som, or KGS – the Kyrgyz Republic currency.

Some Kyrgyz media devoted a number of articles to the activities of maintenance organizations (probably, by local governments' support). A journalist V. Timirbaev ("MSN", 2005, 2006) notes that during the market reforms he became ready to pay "for all" by himself [*instead of waiting for help from the state – G.K.*], but the maintenance organizations do not perform any work. The contract signed in 1998 with a branch of JSC "*Bishkekzhilremont*" (which included Bishkek municipal maintenance organization as described in Chapter II) contained a list of duties of the latter, consisting of 38 types of jobs and services, including the repair of the plumbing and the common property (although those jobs were not performed). In contrast, in the contract dated in 2004 (when JSC *Bishkekzhilremont*'s branches were already transformed to private LLCs), responsibilities of the LLC included only (1) developing a list of jobs, (2) introducing residents to the rules of the apartments and buildings maintenance by residents, (3) the LLC report to House Committee on performed work, and (4) condition assessment of the common property of the building (*ibid*). That is, no maintenance services and jobs were included in the contract.

Nevertheless, over time tariffs of the maintenance companies were increasing. When the LLC once again raised prices, some residents due to a lack of any performed work refused to pay at all (*ibid*). The LLC started sending warnings that contained threats of power outage, even though the electricity bills were paid on time. Residents responded by going to court. Finally, the LLC reduced prices for the previous level (75 *tyiyn*³⁰ per 1 square meter, or about 15 US cents). Timirbayev cites the case of another multifamily building, where residents were paying bills of the LLC during 16 years, but in a building with a leaky roof, refurbishment was never carried out, which led to the rejection of the company.

³⁰ *Tyiyn* – Kyrgyz Republic minor currency, equivalent to 0.01 KGS

These factors formed the negative image of LLCs. In case of rejection of the “old” maintenance companies that do not perform their duties, unit owners are faced with two choices: they can form an HOA or to drop everything to chance (the so called “*beskhozniy*” (mismanaged) buildings).

5.3 THE ESSENCE OF AN HOA

By 2001 only about 20% of the whole country’s multifamily housing stock formed HOAs (Undeland C., 2002), by 2005 – 25% (UNECE, 2010). These figures indicate the rejection of the HOA. Below are ordinary unit owners’ opinions on the issue:

“- I'm thinking of establishing the HOA in the building where I live. Have anyone ever had such experience? (...) (mastercar, 2012)

- If you are ready to drag yourself to the main part of the work - you are welcome! Firstly, collect the 51% [of the homeowners – G.K.] willing to pay HOA (...) 160 som and more (...) Secondly - get ready, there will be individuals who will not join [the HOA – G.K.] and will not pay contributions. You will have to run to the courts to demand [the debts – G.K.]. (...) Then (...) the legal entities in your building (first floor) [commercial units – G.K.], and remodeling... It would be cheaper to me to sell the apartment and to buy a detached house, and I will be responsible only for myself. I have no strength (...) to haul 22 indifferent homeowners and three legal entities into the basement” (nikela, 2012)

“There is the order only in the HOAs with an honest and decent chairman, where most of the work is done voluntarily. But in practice, it turns out there are many dishonest people who want to become chairman of the HOA for personal gain, and after resolving their issues, they quietly either sell up and disappear, not forgetting to take money from the cash register. Or just give up in exercising their power (...). And one more thing, make no mistake, those who did not pay domoupravleniye, will not pay HOA either” (savage, 2012)

These excerpts say that the causes of unwillingness to form an HOA are the obstacles in the operation of an HOA. In order to clarify the sources of the obstacles, it is necessary examine the legal basis for an HOA.

5.3.1 THE LEGAL BASIS FOR AN HOA

Currently, an HOA is the only institution that allows the owners of privatized apartments to make efficient and democratic decisions on management of their common property. The Kyrgyz legislation stipulates that an HOA is established for the joint management and operation of the common property. The latter includes all parts of the multifamily building except for the parts belonging to the certain unit owners. The entrances, staircases, corridors, roofs, attics, technical floors, basements, and land— all these are commonly owned by all unit owners. Land includes the area surrounding the multifamily building, playgrounds, etc., and can pass the state registration of the right of common ownership at the request of unit owners. Engineering equipment for heating, hot and cold water supply, located inside the apartments but serving more than one owner, is also the common property of all unit owners in the given building.

MEMBERSHIP IN HOA

MEMBERSHIP OF NON-RESIDENTIAL UNIT OWNERS

Multifamily buildings in the Kyrgyz Republic often consist of both residential (intended for living) and non-residential (commercial, e.g., pharmacies, shops, hair salons, etc., usually located on the ground floor) units. The owners of each unit have the same duties with respect to the HOA. However, according to the Law³¹, only the owners of apartments (residential units) are considered as homeowners. That is, the owners of non-residential units are not members of the HOAs; they can become members of the HOA only with the consent of the general meeting of the homeowners.

This provision of the Law is different from the generally accepted world practice, when the owner's membership does not depend on the purpose of the unit. It

³¹ In this chapter, all references to the legislation belong to the law “On Homeowners Associations” unless otherwise stated.

also does not comply with the aforementioned norm of the Law, stipulating that the common property is jointly owned by all unit owners.

MANDATORY VS. VOLUNTARY MEMBERSHIP OF UNIT OWNERS IN THE HOA

Article 3 of the Law stipulates that unit owner cannot be forced to become a member of the HOA. As described in the previous chapters, according to the experience of other countries and various experts, this provision can be a main cause of the failure of the reforms. Developed by the United Nations (UN), the “Guidelines on Condominium Ownership of Housing for Countries in Transition” (2003) suggests to consider such provisions “*only as unfortunate cases where national constitutional arguments against compulsory membership in owners’ associations prevail*” (p. 8). Probably, here the UN had in mind the cases of the Russian Federation and Ukraine described in Chapter III, where mandatory membership in the HOA was hindered by the norm of the respective Constitutions. More precisely, article 30 of the Russian Constitution states that everyone has the right to unite³² and that *no one can be compelled to join a union and to remain in it*. Article 36 of the Constitution of Ukraine containing similar provision has also caused repeal of the mandatory membership in the HOA (Lipman, 2012).

However, article 35 of the Constitution of the Kyrgyz Republic, establishing the right of everyone to unite freely, does not prohibit the compulsion to join the union (association). All unit owners are required to participate in the maintenance regardless of whether they are members of the HOA or not. The maintenance costs are shared between the owners prorated to his / her share in the common property (i.e., the share of the floor area of the unit to the total area of all units in the given building) (Art. 26). Thus, the establishment of the mandatory membership of all unit owners in the HOA should not entail on them any additional burden. The aforementioned Guidelines (p. 13) recommend reflecting the requirement of

³² In Russian “*obyedineniye*” (can be translated as both “union” and “association”).

mandatory membership in HOA in the national legislation, referring to the fact that such a rule is present in the respective laws of the countries of Western Europe and the United States.

PROCEDURES OF THE FORMATION OF AN HOA AND DOCUMENTS REGISTRATION

According to the Law, an HOA can be formed by the will of at least a 51 percent of homeowners (i.e., apartment owners) in a multifamily building. The constituent meeting may be convened by a group of owners. If the apartment is rented, tenants who are not authorized by the owner do not have voting rights and are not entitled to participate in the management of the HOA. HOA as a legal entity is subject to the state registration in the local branches of the Ministry of Justice.

MANDATORY VS. VOLUNTARY FORMATION OF HOA

The pivotal factor in the success of the reforms of housing management in some countries in transition was a legislative requirement on the formation of the HOA in each multifamily building. Legislation of the Kyrgyz Republic does not contain such a provision: article 248 of the Civil Code states that the apartment owners *form* an HOA, that is not a peremptory norm; article 3 of the Law stipulates that an HOA *can be formed*. Thus, the holding of housing reforms in the Kyrgyz Republic is much complicated by the lack of basic requirements on the mandatory HOA. Since it is about the safety of the homes of citizens, which is one of the primary needs of the human being, the adoption of strict rules seems warranted. It also corresponds to common practice and the recommendations of international donor organizations and experts:

“Homeowners associations are core institutions to facilitate housing management and maintenance. It is crucial for a successful implementation of any new strategy to have access to the greatest possible number of housing associations. It is recommended to change the Law on Condominiums³³ to make the formation of owners associations obligatory for all existing multifamily residential buildings.

³³ The Law on HOAs.

There are no major legal obstacles to achieving this goal” (UNECE (2010) p. 75, recommendations for the Kyrgyz Republic).

REGISTRATION OF THE SHARE OF EACH UNIT OWNER IN THE COMMON PROPERTY

The share of each owner in the common property is the ratio of the area of the owner’s unit to the total area of all owners’ units. Share in the common property determines the amount of payments of each owner required for the maintenance of the common property and other general expenses. Currently, the certificates of titles³⁴ to the units do not contain information on the share of the common property (interview with *Gosregister*³⁵ staff). The Law on HOAs stipulates that the Registration Card³⁶ for a unit *contains* (instead of “*must contain*”) information about the size of the owner’s share in the common property in accordance with the legal documents (art. 8). However, usually this requirement is not met. Neither deeds³⁷, nor Registration Cards contain information on the common property share. The above information is entered into the Registration Card after the HOA calculates the share of the common property (in percentages) and submits the report of the HOA’s general meeting to the *Gosregister*, which typically does not occur (interview with *Gosregister* staff). Thus, the title to the common property is only defined by the Law (which not everyone knows) without explicit specification of the share in the documents (although according Article 4 of the Law “On state registration of rights to real property and transactions with it”, a title is subject to mandatory state registration). The exact calculation of each unit owner’s share with entering of these data in the title documents may raise awareness of unit owners of their rights and responsibilities regarding the common property.

³⁴ Title (in this study) - property right to real estate.

³⁵ *Gosregister* - the state body authorized for the registration of real property.

³⁶ Registration Card (*registratsionnaya kartochnka*) – an internal document of *Gosregister* containing a record of real estate unit, the rights to it and its legal owners. A Registration Card is put on each unit of real estate (the Law “On state registration of rights to real property and transactions with it”).

³⁷ Deeds (in this study) - agreement on the transfer \ obtaining the rights to real estate (such as a contract of sale of real estate). D. is the basis for the state registration of property rights.

THE GOVERNING BODIES OF AN HOA

GENERAL MEETING

Pursuant to Article 19, the supreme governing body of an HOA is a general meeting, in which every unit has one vote. The general meeting is competent if attended by at least 51% of HOA's members, but its decisions are mandatory for all unit owners. General meeting's powers include (1) election and dismissal of the HOA's executives, (2) approval of the HOA's Charter and amendments to it, the annual report of the Board, the annual budget and special contributions not covered by the latter, (3) hiring a manager, etc. Decisions require a simple majority or 75% of the votes present at the meeting (depending on the issue), except for voting on loans that is described later.

General meeting must be held at least once a year. Notice of the general meeting shall be given to the members of the HOA in writing. The unit owner has the right to entrust his/her vote to someone else through a power of attorney drawn up in writing. Absentee voting is not stipulated in the legislation.

OTHER GOVERNING BODIES OF AN HOA

When forming the HOA, the chairperson, the board and the audit committee are elected by the constituent meeting of the HOA; after formation - by the simple majority of those present at the general meeting. The executives of the HOA are elected for a term of 2 years. The board manages the HOA between general meetings and carries out all powers of the HOA, except for those within the exclusive competence of the general meeting.

The executives must be the members of the HOA. This limitation has dual consequences. On the one hand, the probability of serious violations of the executives is low because of their personal interest in improving the condition of the building

and because of social ties with neighbors in the building. On the other hand, not every building has a unit owner with the necessary managerial skills.

As a consequence, the abuse of power and immorality of chairpersons taking place in Russia is also observed in the Kyrgyz HOAs. The absence of an audit committee (whose formation is optional) may lead to the usurpation by the HOA's chairperson. The other obstacle is that in practice the audit committees of the HOAs often do not perform their functions.

FINANCES OF AN HOA

Solvency of an HOA is the cornerstone of the effectiveness of all its activities. HOA as a non-profit organization may engage in economic activities, using the proceeds for the needs of the building. However, not all HOAs have such opportunities. In these circumstances, the presence of the leverage on defaulters and the access to external sources of funding are of particular importance.

THE LEVERAGE ON THE FREE-RIDERS

In case of the delay of payments of monthly contributions, the general meeting (the simple majority of those present at the meeting) can set penalties, the amount of which cannot exceed 30% of the total debt. If the debtor continues to refuse to pay, HOA can file a lawsuit. Given the fact that the trial is a lengthy and costly process, and taking into account the bureaucratic realities of the Kyrgyz judicial system, this form of debt collection can hardly be effective for the HOAs.

In addition, lack of leverage on free-riders has a negative impact on the rest of unit owners, as they have to cover the costs of maintaining the common property of both themselves and the defaulters (furthermore, some conscientious payers may reasonably object and refuse to pay the bills). To overcome these difficulties, it is preferable to give the HOAs adequate powers, such as the imposition of collateral on the debtor's property (following the experience of CEE countries). UNECE (2010)

notes about Kyrgyz Republic's constitutional guarantees of the universal right to housing which preclude the imposition of lien on the unit in case of the debt. Imposition of a lien on the housing is undesirable also due to the current economic situation (such as unemployment and poverty). Thus, it can be more expedient to practice imposing a lien on the debtor's personal property (such as a car, electrical appliances, etc.) with the subsequent sale and repay of the debt to the HOA.

THE ACCESS TO THE GOVERNMENT GRANTS AND BANK LOANS

In Hungary, the lowering of the threshold for voting for obtaining refurbishment loan to 50% significantly increased activities of the HOAs. In contrast, in the Kyrgyz Republic, the decision to obtain a loan requires the consent of all members of the HOA (though arithmetically more than 50% of all members of the HOA in Hungary, where all unit owners are members of an HOA, can be equivalent to 100% of the HOA members in the Kyrgyz Republic, where HOA can consist only of 51% of unit owners). Here, the absence of a general membership can also be a negative factor for credit institutions, as it can result in a weak guarantee of repayment. Creation of favorable conditions will also help the development of the practice of bank loans for HOAs (e.g. tax cuts for such loans as in some CEE countries).

The absence of the HOA's reserve fund (its formation is optional, Art. 25) aimed for a major refurbishment of the building will certainly result in (1) failure to conduct timely refurbishment, and (2) in the need of one-time collection of large amounts of money in case of the necessity of urgent refurbishment works. In addition, the absence of a reserve fund is another negative factor for credit institutions. Reflection of a requirement for mandatory establishment of reserve fund in each multifamily building in the national legislation seems to be a necessary measure.

Bishkek local government provides grant support to HOAs, paying up to 50% of the refurbishment costs. The details of the grant program are described later.

PROVISIONS OF THE DRAFT HOUSING CODE

Housing legal relations hitherto are regulated by the Housing Code of the Soviet period. The draft Housing Code (hereinafter “the bill”) was developed several years ago and currently is under consideration. The following are the main differences of the bill from existing legislation.

Management methods provided in the bill are similar to the Russian ones:

- owners’ direct management,
- an HOA,
- a cooperative,
- a manager (individual entrepreneur or a company),
- and specialized public authority.

Thus, the types of management methods will be limited (there is no reference to “other methods stipulated by the legislation” as in the current law). Building management method shall be chosen at a general meeting of unit owners during the six months after the bill has gone into force. After this period, the right to hold public procurements for the selection of a manager is supposed to pass to the executive bodies of local governments. The order of public procurements is to be determined by the representative bodies of local governments. In addition, the executive bodies of local governments will be responsible for (1) organizing and holding of training courses for building managers and (2) bringing owners who refuse to pay the cost of management and maintenance of the common property to administrative responsibility. The last provision may facilitate the debt collection activities of the HOAs, as proceedings in the local governments’ administrative commissions are of shorter duration than those of the judicial ones.

According to Article 23 of the bill, the title to the share in the common property will be subject to state registration. Perhaps, the legislators will adopt separate

regulations governing registration procedures. Unlike current law, article 34 of the bill provides that HOA is formed by the owners of both residential and non-residential units. However, the article also states that the owners “*have the right*” (that is “*may*”, but not “*must*”) to join HOAs.

UNECE (2010, p. 47) says the bill is based on the Housing Code of the Russian Federation (e.g. a variety of management methods and the absence of the requirement of mandatory membership in the HOA). Given the difficulties faced by the stakeholders in the Russian Federation, the adoption of this bill in its current condition can lead to a similar result.

5.3.2 EFFORTS OF THE BISHKEK LOCAL GOVERNMENT ON PROMOTION AND SUPPORT OF HOAS

Bishkek is the largest city of the Kyrgyz Republic. Occupying an area of 160 sq. km., the population is about 1 million people (about 1/5 of the total population). Most of Bishkek multifamily buildings were built in the Soviet era (Figure V-8), and due to the reasons previously discussed are currently in need of refurbishment. Typically, multifamily buildings in Bishkek consist of 50-120 apartments.

FIGURE V-8: BUILDINGS CONSISTING OF MORE THAN ONE DWELLING BY PERIOD OF CONSTRUCTION, BISHKEK

Source: National Statistical Committee of the Kyrgyz Republic, 2011 (composed by author)

Bishkek local government includes *Kenesh* (the representative body, hereinafter a “Council”) and mayor's office (the executive body). The latter comprises its structural and territorial divisions.

BISHKEK LOCAL GOVERNMENTS’ GRANTS FOR REFURBISHMENT OF THE COMMON PROPERTY OF MULTIFAMILY BUILDINGS³⁸

Bishkek local government started the Incentive Grants Program (hereinafter an “IG Program”) in 2005 through enacting the city Council resolution, approving the “Provisional Regulations on the Financing of Projects Aimed at the Development of the city by Incentive (Shared) Grants”, 2004. The program is currently regulated by modified resolutions (regulations) enacted in 2009³⁹.

The main of the aims of the IG program is the development and support of citizens’ initiatives on refurbishment of common property of multifamily buildings. The main source of the IG Program is the Bishkek municipal budget. Only legal entities may act as applicants. The organizations that can compete for grants include HOAs, housing cooperatives, and other non-profit organizations. Incentive Grants are also provided to public schools and detached housing areas, but those projects are not the subject of this study.

In order to select the projects, Bishkek local government form a Grant Committee consisting of local government’s representatives (see Appendix A on the mechanism of IG Program). The Grant Committee annually identifies the proportions of the co-financing by the applicants and priority directions⁴⁰ of the program. The latter generally consist of the most pressing issues (Table V-4). In 2012, priority directions included refurbishment of the roofs, street lighting, elevators, irrigation,

³⁸ This section is largely based on the Program Progress Reports and presentations provided by the Bishkek City Development Agency (“*Agentstvo razvitiya goroda Bishkek*”), a structural division of the mayor's office.

³⁹ This section is based on those regulations.

⁴⁰ In Russian “*prioritetniye napravleniya*”.

staircases, etc. The City Development Agency (hereinafter the “Agency”) is in charge of the IG Program implementation.

TABLE V-4: IMPLEMENTED PROJECTS⁴¹ (INCLUDING NON-MULTIFAMILY BUILDINGS’ PROJECTS)

Project type	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2011	in total
Roof	16	41	50	10	21	19	157
<i>School buildings’ refurbishment</i>	1	12	16	2	1	2	34
Outdoor lighting	0	8	4	-	-	-	12
Elevator	0	2	3	-	1	2	8
Irrigation	3	-	4	-	-	-	7
Staircase	1	-	4	-	-	-	5
Heating and hot water supply	0	-	3	-	-	2	5
Innovative projects	4	7	4	-	-	-	15
Facade and interpanel joints	0	-	2	-	1	-	3
Others	6	8	3	-	2	1	20
In total	31	78	93	12	26	26	266

Source: City Development Agency report, 2012; composed by author)

For the period 2005–2011, 104 (i.e., 12%) out of total 774 HOAs and housing cooperatives formed by the time obtained Incentive Grants. However, as the number of applications from one HOA or housing cooperative is not limited, some active organizations obtain several grants in a single year.

Initially, in some cases Incentive Grants were provided in the absence of or with a low amount of co-financing. In addition, Incentive Grants were issued to

⁴¹ Data for 2004 was not available.

commercial maintenance organizations too. Subsequently, it was decided to provide Incentive Grants only to HOAs or housing cooperatives (for multifamily buildings) and to support only those applications that provide at least 50% co-financing by the applicant (Figure V-9). Such decisions were supposed to encourage the formation of HOAs and stimulate their vigorous activity. In 2012, the grant amount was up to 400,000 *som* (an average salary in Bishkek is about 10,000 *som*).

FIGURE V-9: ANNUAL AGGREGATE GRANT AMOUNT AND RATIO TO THE CO-FINANCE AMOUNT⁴²

(Source: City Development Agency report (2012), composed by author)

RAISING AWARENESS AMONG RESIDENTS OF MULTIFAMILY BUILDINGS ON THE FORMATION OF HOAS⁴³

Since the end of 2010, the Bishkek mayor's office conducted mass targeted communication with the residents of multifamily buildings where HOAs had not been formed yet (e.g., during the 3rd quarter 2012, Bishkek mayor's office held 68 outreach meetings with residents). Largely due to the aforementioned ongoing work, in Bishkek the share of multifamily buildings that formed the HOA exceeded 50% (excluding hostels, buildings with more than 70% non-residential units and

⁴² In 2005 and 2010, the IG Program did not run due to the political situation; in 2008, the acceptance of applications has been limited due to difficulties with city budget.

⁴³ This section is largely based on the HOA Formation Progress Reports provided by the Agency

vedomstvennyi (public enterprises’) buildings). In 2011, 95 HOAs were formed, in 2012 - 126 HOAs. Figure V-10 shows the situation in multifamily building management as of September 2012.

FIGURE V-10: MULTIFAMILY BUILDINGS IN BISHKEK BY MANAGEMENT METHOD (AS OF SEPTEMBER 2012)

Source: City Development Agency report, 2012; composed by author

However, this state should be perceived as an intermediate result. Comparison with the distribution of management methods in Hungary (see Figure IV-7), where the HOA is formed in each building, but the vast majority of them engage the services of professional managers, recalls the need to train housing managers in the Kyrgyz Republic.

BISHKEK MUNICIPAL SUBSIDIES FOR UTILITY SERVICES

Bishkek local government is providing citizens with subsidies for utility services⁴⁴. It is a targeted social aid, where local government pays the bills of low-income families for utility services. Subsidized utility services include central heating and gas supply, hot and cold water supply, solid waste removal, and maintenance of elevators. This program provides significant support for the so-called “house poor” that may ultimately be considered as a support for the HOAs. The inclusion of

⁴⁴ In Russian “*jilishniye subsidii*”

contributions to the HOA in the list of subsidized services can help both needy owners and HOAs, partially removing a problem of low payment collection. However, the difficulties with the implementation of this proposal are likely to take place, since the subsidy program applies to *public* utilities.

Despite the huge advocacy activities and financial support of HOAs and unit owners (however, within the available resources) conducted by the Bishkek mayor's office, presumably the maximum number of HOAs that could be formed under the so-called "voluntary-coercive order" ("*dobrovolno-prinuditelny poryadok*") has been reached. Without the appropriate legal framework at the national level, the local authorities have to make significant efforts to encourage unit owners to form an HOA. However, as shown in the case of Bishkek, no amount of local effort can achieve a hundred percent result.

5.4 SUMMARY

During the housing reform process in the 1990s, many important decisions had been taken, including the transfer of home ownership to the sitting tenants, introduction of HOAs as legal entities, privatization of housing maintenance companies, registration of title to the surrounding land, and others. However, the "stretching" of the reforms for decades and inadequate legislation have not allowed finishing the job.

Privatization of housing maintenance companies aimed to improve the quality of their services. Unlike state-owned monopolies, the actors of the free market should be self-regulated. However, the de-monopolization without the simultaneous development of a competitive market could not succeed. The result was a degradation of services of the LLCs. In turn, it led to the rejection of the LLCs by some unit owners. Others continue to pay LLCs' bills in the absence of any work performed. In the absence of large-scale outreach work, unit owners were not able to reorient

independently to the new conditions. The online forums, where a number of threads and comments regarding studying problem were posted, confirms the assumption about citizens' low awareness of the changes taking place. Nevertheless, not all of the unit owners made further decisions on housing management, leaving things to chance.

The granting of powers on the selection of management companies to the local governments (following Russian experience), proposed by the draft Housing Code, seems to be a necessary innovation in the background of passivity of unit owners. Nevertheless, without prior training of adequate numbers of competent housing managers, housing management sector cannot properly function. It is unlikely to find in each building an owner suitable for the role of HOA chairperson as a manager of a real estate complex. In contrast, the role of HOA chairperson as a representative of all the owners applying for the services of a professional manager is less stressful. Job creation is an additional positive aspect of training and hiring of the building managers. At the same time, the current HOAs' chairpersons also require training (according to the Agency, they actively participate in the training courses organized by the Bishkek local government and international donor organizations working on this issue).

The failure to take responsibility by each stakeholder and subsequent inadequate maintenance of multifamily buildings is due to the uncertainty of the legislation on housing management. The similarity of the Kyrgyz and Russian legislation regarding non-mandatory HOA and other rules is explained by historical and linguistic similarities⁴⁵. However, the Kyrgyz Republic should learn from the experience of countries successfully implemented housing reforms (particularly CEE). Today, HOA is the only body that pushes owners to unite and to manage their multifamily buildings. First, in the HOA, decisions are made based on democratic principles. Second, HOA is a legal entity representing the unit owners, which is important when

⁴⁵ In the Kyrgyz Republic, the Russian language is endowed with the status of an official language and is used together with the Kyrgyz language.

entering into contracts and when applying to state agencies including the courts. Establishing a mandatory HOA in each multifamily building and mandatory membership of unit owners in the HOA seems to be the most appropriate solution. This decision should be accompanied by setting penalties for non-compliance.

Another negative factor is the lack of information about the share in the common property in the units' deeds and other documents. Unless such information becomes obvious, it is difficult to require unit owners to perform his / her responsibilities.

Some unit owners continue to reject the formation of HOA due to the unwillingness to take responsibility, the usurpation and abuse of powers by some chairpersons that produces a negative impression. The activities of existing HOAs are limited by the absence of funds due to the widespread free-riding and a lack of effective mechanism for debt collection. All of this resulted in a low HOA formation dynamics. The study of reasons for reluctance to form HOA is continued in the next chapter.

In a crisis of multifamily building management, the efforts of local authorities to support HOAs are remarkable. However, the experts say (and Bishkek case proved it) that the reform of housing management is impossible to complete only by local efforts. The national legislation is in need of major improvement.

In view of the undoubted importance of multifamily housing for the country, the solution of existing problems deserves the attention and the combined efforts of all stakeholders. The perception of the main stakeholder – leaders of the multifamily buildings – is detailed in the next chapter.

VI. THE EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS: A CASE OF BISHKEK MULTIFAMILY BUILDINGS

6.1 THE BACKGROUND OF THE SURVEY

The purpose of the survey was to confirm or to challenge the assumptions, to identify hidden problems, and to compare the effectiveness of different methods of housing management. The questionnaire, drawn up by the author, included questions on the most acute problems of the common property state and its management (see Appendix B for the original (Russian) and English (translated) versions of the questionnaire). The questionnaire consisted of 35 questions, both open- and close-ended. In turn, some of questions included sub questions. Most of the answer options to the questions, which used the Likert scale, rated from one to four (e.g., “strongly agree – agree – disagree – strongly disagree”). When drawing up the questionnaire, the provision of the minimum impact on the respondents' opinions and comfort, not exceeding their daily occurrences, was of paramount importance.

According the Bishkek Development Agency, the total number of multifamily buildings by 2012 was exceeding 2300. During the study, opinions of 56 leaders of the multifamily buildings in the Bishkek were surveyed through the questionnaire. Gender distribution of the respondents was as follows: eight respondents (15%) - male, 45 respondents (85%) - female⁴⁶. Most of the respondents (61%) were the leaders of the cooperatives and HOAs, which coincides with the share of such buildings in Bishkek (Figures V-10 and VI-11). The survey included questions about the managed building, the state of its common property, difficulties faced by the leaders, perception about the HOA and LLC, and some demographic questions.

⁴⁶ In the Kyrgyz Republic, the predominance of women among the leaders of multifamily buildings is common.

Note: The management method of one of the respondents was not specified.

FIGURE VI-11: NUMBER OF RESPONDENTS BY BUILDING MANAGEMENT METHOD
Source: Analysis of survey data

6.1 EVALUATION OF THE STATE OF THE COMMON PROPERTY

The criteria for the evaluation of the common property ranged from “very bad” to “very good” (Figure VI-12). “(Very) good” and “(very) bad” options scored about the same number of responses. That is, about half of the respondents noted (very) poor state of the common property.

FIGURE VI-12: THE STATE OF THE COMMON PROPERTY
Source: Analysis of survey data

There is a difference in the state of the common property depending on the type of the facility. In the relatively large number of respondent's buildings, roof, exterior walls and pipes (approximately 30, 20 and 15%, respectively) are in a "very bad state". This can be explained by the fact that (1) such facilities wear out most quickly because they either protect the building from the outside influences, or hold utilities, (2) unit owners do not see these facilities directly and daily (as opposed to, for example, the porch), so they hardly give money to refurbish them, and (3) maintenance of these facilities is usually rather expensive. However, these facilities seem the most important for the preservation of the building. In contrast, in 65 percent of the responses, the state of the yard was rated as "good" and "very good", probably due to its lower amortization.

As a one-time collection of money for the refurbishment of expensive facilities is difficult, regular accumulation of monthly contributions in the reserve fund of the building seems to be the best solution. Similar to the sinking fund for business enterprises, the reserve fund for the management of each multifamily buildings should be required.

Respondent No. 20, explaining the poor state of the managed building, wrote that they *"have not carried out major refurbishment due to the reluctance of unit owners to hand over the money, as they live thinking only about the current day"*. In contrast, the respondent No. 49 who rated the state of all the facilities as "very good" specified the reason, *"the participation of the unit owners in the management of the common property and the desire to live well"*. Paradoxically, the leaders of the buildings with the opposite state of the common property indicated one reason - unit owners. According the leaders, the difference lies in the attitude of unit owners. This raises the question of what or who forms the attitude of unit owners for maintenance of common property (it is discussed later).

It is noteworthy that respondent No. 49 answered to the question about the reason why they formed the HOA in 2006: “*the emergency state of the common property*”. Due to the efforts of the HOA, in 7 years the state of the common property significantly improved - from emergency state to a very good state.

THE STATE OF THE COMMON PROPERTY BY THE MANAGEMENT METHOD

Average scores⁴⁷ of the assessed common property (1 to 4, from “very poor” to “very good” respectively, i.e., the mean score was 2.5) is rather different depending on the method of building management (Figure VI-13). The lowest scores were given by the leaders of the buildings managed by the LLCs - from 1.5 to 2.4, that is, all buildings managed by the LLCs were scored below the mean score (2.5). These data suggest that in the buildings, managed by former *JEKs*, in general the maintenance of the buildings was not conducted.

FIGURE VI-13: THE STATE OF THE COMMON PROPERTY BY TYPE OF MANAGEMENT

Source: Analysis of survey data

The highest average score (3.5 to 4) was observed only in some questionnaires completed by the leaders of some HOAs. Thereby, in the buildings managed by the

⁴⁷ To calculate the average score, the scores of all facilities of multifamily buildings were summarized.

HOAs without the involvement of former *JEKs*, the state of the common property is relatively good. Additionally, all the respondents who pointed to the “very good” condition of the roof (the roofs are most often in the poorest state, see Figure 12) were the leaders of the cooperatives or HOAs, and half of them wrote that earlier they received municipal Incentive Grants for the refurbishment of the roof (respondents No. 49 and 50).

6.2 CHALLENGES OF BUILDING MANAGEMENT

The purpose of this question was the assessment of the severance of the problems that building managers face. Almost 60% of the respondents considered the following issues as (very) challenging: (1) the state of the common property, (2) the convening of the general meeting, and (3) the reluctance of unit owners to pay contributions for the maintenance of the building (Figure VI-14). Moreover, a third of those surveyed said the reluctance to pay the fees was a “very major” challenge. At the same time, the low level of contributions is, according to the leaders of the buildings, a “(very) minor” problem (50% of the responses).

FIGURE VI-14: THE SIGNIFICANCE OF THE CHALLENGES OF BUILDING MANAGEMENT

Source: Analysis of survey data

THE POOR STATE OF THE COMMON PROPERTY

The poor state of the common property is a (very) significant problem for more than 70% of the respondents of all management methods (Figure VI-15). The exception was the HOAs, where less than 50% considered the poor state of the common property as a (very) significant problem.

FIGURE VI-15: COMMON PROPERTY’S POOR STATE: THE SIGNIFICANCE OF THE PROBLEM BY MANAGEMENT METHOD

Source: Analysis of survey data

These data may indicate that the HOAs are directly involved in the maintenance of the common property, including a major refurbishment. The unit owners who formed the HOA are those who *decided to manage* their common property.

At the other management methods, the appropriate and timely maintenance activities may not be carried out due to the reluctance of the unit owners including their leaders. Respondent No. 11 explained his / her views on the seriousness of the problem of poor state of the common property:

“The buildings built after 1963 have been designed to operate for 25 years (it was a concomitant housing, i.e., after 25 years (...) the panel [panel buildings – G.K.] should have been demolished). (...) We live in the buildings that already served their time. The entire panel is cracked. The government wants people to take responsibility for housing, which should have been eliminated. (...)You cannot shift the

responsibility for such housing on the shoulders of the people! The government should develop a project to resolve the situation. It is bad that again you are trying to develop legislation to force to take responsibility for this housing"

Thus, some owners still believe the government is responsible for the maintenance of the buildings, considering themselves as the victims of a situation, forced to live in substandard public housing. Certainly, in the Soviet period, the government was responsible for these buildings. However, at the same time, the state was its owner. Enjoying full rights to privatized apartments, some owners do not recognize the rights and responsibilities to the common property surrounding the apartment. While complaining about the poor quality of buildings, such owners do not want to admit that timely refurbishment can prevent the deterioration of the building.

The need to change the attitude of non-independent unit owners towards the problem is well known to all stakeholders in the Kyrgyz Republic. Welfare mentality can be influenced through wide dissemination of the best experiences. Simultaneously, the government could continue to convey the information that (1) not the government but unit owners are responsible for their own housing, including the common property; and (2) the (local) governments are already assisting those in need and active unit owners (e.g., Incentive Grants and Utility Subsidies Programs).

RELUCTANCE TO PAY CONTRIBUTIONS

Figure VI-16 shows that the reluctance to pay contributions is a serious problem for all management methods⁴⁸. In contrast to the author's original assumption that the buildings managed by cooperatives are more organized, the survey found that for cooperatives, free-riding is a very serious problem as well.

⁴⁸ As a general rule, in the buildings led by the House Committees, the monthly contributions are not collected.

FIGURE VI-16: RELUCTANCE TO PAY

Source: Analysis of survey data

Interesting conclusions can be drawn when comparing the data from Figure VI-17, which says that the cooperatives have the lowest level of owners' participation. These findings indicate that the active participation of unit owners in the management of the building has a positive effect on the willingness to pay contributions for the maintenance.

FIGURE VI-17: UNIT OWNERS' PARTICIPATION IN BUILDING MANAGEMENT

Source: Analysis of survey data

PROPOSALS TO INCREASE CONTRIBUTION RATE

The perception of the respondents regarding the increase of the contributions rate differs depending on the management method (Figure VI-18). Respondents, who agreed with increasing, cite the lack of funds for maintenance of the building and the rise in prices of construction materials. HOAs' leaders more often than others consider the increase of the contribution rates necessary.

According to the survey, the monthly contributions average 1.5-2.5 KGS per square meter of the unit. The average floor size of the apartment in Bishkek is about 40-50 sq. meters. Thus, the average contribution rate is 80-100 KGS, or about 1% of the average monthly wage in the city. More than 70% of respondents that support increases of the monthly contributions, have offered the increase on 50-100%.

FIGURE VI-18: PERCEPTION ABOUT INCREASING MONTHLY CONTRIBUTIONS

Source: Analysis of survey data

About half of the respondents (40-60% depending on the management method) objected the increase of contribution rate, specifying the unit owners' poverty as an obstacle. State (local) subsidies, paying the monthly contributions of the needy unit owners to an HOA, would support both parties.

6.3 QUALITY OF THE LLCs' SERVICES

The vast majority of the respondents gave a negative assessment of the quality of LLCs' services, with more than half of the respondents indicated "very low quality" (Figure VI-19).

FIGURE VI-19: QUALITY OF LLCs' SERVICES

Source: Analysis of survey data

This opinion was expressed by the leaders of the buildings maintained by the LLCs at the time of the survey and those who have already refused their services (Figure VI-20)⁴⁹. These data, in addition to the views set out in Chapter V (posts in online forums and newspaper articles) confirm information about a significant reduction in services of the LLCs.

⁴⁹ Cooperatives were not included in Figure 20 because they initially manage their buildings by themselves.

FIGURE VI-20: QUALITY OF LLCs' SERVICES BY ITS CURRENT AND EX-USERS OF SERVICES

Source: Analysis of survey data

6.4 HOAs: FORMATION AND ACTIVITIES

As expected, a relatively large proportion of the surveyed HOAs were formed when the mass outreach work was carried out (Figure VI-21). In 2012, the huge propaganda of HOAs was carried out by the Bishkek mayor's office. In 2006, at the request of the Bishkek local government, the Soros Foundation organized a series of the workshops with the provision of the manuals on the activities of the HOAs (interview with City Development Agency staff). This suggests a rather high effectiveness of the propaganda of an HOA.

FIGURE VI-21: YEARS WHEN SURVEYED HOAs WERE FORMED
Source: Analysis of survey data

THE NEEDS OF THE HOAs IN SUPPORT

The answer options to this question varied from 1 to 3 (Figure VI-22). In general, almost all of the forms of support, mentioned in the questionnaire, were assessed as necessary. As expected, most of the respondents indicated a grant support as “very necessary”. On the other hand, rather large number of respondents expressed skepticism about strengthening the powers of the HOAs, which may indicate the continuing hopes of support from the outside. There is a need to explain to the building’s leaders that independence and self-sufficiency are more sustainable factors. However, some respondents are aware of it. For example, the respondent No. 25 suggested giving more powers to the leaders of the buildings, having said that “*it will solve all the problems in the short term*”.

FIGURE VI-22: WHAT KIND OF SUPPORT HOAS NEED

Source: Analysis of survey data

Additionally, the respondent No. 49 proposed to reduce taxes of the HOA’s hired workers, which are currently equal to the taxes of the business organizations (while an HOA is a non-profit organization). Several respondents voiced a problem of demarcation of the land surrounding the multifamily building, with requests to simplify the procedures and to reduce the cost of this service. These proposals can be considered when developing legislation on the housing management and other relative law.

Despite the fact that the majority of respondents (except for HOAs) expect to receive grant support, many leaders of the buildings are still not aware of the IG Program (Figure VI-23). This data suggests Bishkek mayor’s office to strengthen information support of the Incentive Grants Program.

FIGURE VI-23: AWARENESS ON THE IG PROGRAM

Source: Analysis of survey data

FORMATION OF AN HOA

Most of the respondents agreed with the necessity of the formation of an HOA (52% agree, 17% strongly agree), while only 7% of respondents strongly opposed. However, opinion among respondents differs greatly depending on the current management method (Figure VI-24). More than 60% of the house committees and 50% of the cooperatives believe HOA unnecessary.

FIGURE VI-24: OPINION ON THE NECESSITY OF THE FORMATION OF AN HOA

Source: Analysis of survey data

As a rationale for the formation of the HOAs, respondents indicated to (1) self-government and independent decision-making (35%), (2) willingness of the residents (22%), and (3) LLCs’ failure to comply with its obligations (9%). Transparency in the use of funds of an HOA and independence are considered as positive aspects of the HOA. The irresponsibility of the owners was most often listed as negative aspect of the HOA. Thus, the neglect of unit owners, and most likely - lack of leverage on them, is one of the causes of the reluctance of some owners (or rather, the buildings’ leaders) to form an HOA.

In addition, the data on the age of the respondents indirectly confirmed the assumption that another reason for the refusal to form an HOA (despite the information and financial support from Bishkek mayor's office) is the ingrained habit to the Soviet housing management system and the reluctance to changes. Many of the buildings except HOAs (30-60% depending on the management method) are managed by leaders over 61 (Figure VI-25). That is, those leaders were born in the 1950s and earlier, i.e., 40 or more years before the collapse of the Soviet Union. In contrast, 25% of the HOAs’ leaders represent the younger generation (under 40), and only 10% - at the age of 61 and older.

FIGURE VI-25: AGE CATEGORIES OF RESPONDENTS

Source: Analysis of survey data

During the interview, one of the chairpersons of the house committee answered to the question why they have not formed an HOA yet: “*Why do I need these problems [building’s problems – G.K.]? If I form an HOA, I will have to solve them and to be responsible for them*” (the building managed by this house committee was relatively recently built and is located in one of the most prestigious areas of the city, i.e., it is inhabited mainly by wealthy people, thus there is no issue of unit owners’ poverty). Possibly, the reason is as follows. The current leaders who refuse to form HOA (i.e., house committees’ chairpersons) do not want to take the responsibility for the building and at the same time do not want to lose their position. Therefore, they probably carry out anti-propaganda of HOA among unit owners in their buildings.

When asked about the reasons for the reluctance to form an HOA, the majority (60-85% depending on the management method) reported (1) un-readiness- and (2) unwillingness of unit owners to take responsibility for the common property, and (3) passivity of the owners (Figure VI-26). There were comments such as “*reluctance [of building leaders – G.K.] to collect money*”, “*nobody needs this headache*”, and “*no one wants to take responsibility*”. In contrast, the bureaucratic obstacles when passing the state registration of the HOA, in more than 80% were marked as “(very) rare cause”. These data support the assumption that the cause for the relatively low dynamics of the formation of the HOA is subjective reasons, to be exact - the reluctance of unit owners and building leaders to take responsibility for the maintenance of the building. To change this attitude, the explanations about the consequences of the inaction in the maintenance of the building (e.g., reducing the attractiveness of the apartment and, accordingly, its value, and the possible unsuitability for the stay) can be held.

FIGURE VI-26: CAUSES OF UNWILLINGNESS TO FORM AN HOA
Source: Analysis of survey data

EFFECTIVENESS OF THE TOOLS TO PROMOTE HOAS

In general, all means to promote HOAs indicated in the questionnaire were found as effective (Figure VI-27). However, respondents believe that grant support is the most effective one. Nevertheless, when compared to Figure VI-21 (“Years when surveyed HOAs were formed”), the opposite becomes clear. IG Program is implemented since 2004, but the high level of the formation of the HOAs was observed only in the years when considerable outreach work was carried out.

FIGURE VI-27: EFFECTIVENESS OF THE TOOLS TO PROMOTE HOAS
Source: Analysis of survey data

CHANGES FOLLOWED THE FORMATION OF THE HOA

The majority of leaders of the HOAs indicated the improvement in all of the problematic issues listed in Figure VI-28.

FIGURE VI-28: CHANGES AFTER FORMATION OF THE HOA

Source: Analysis of survey data

The following are the remarks of some of the respondents:

“The residents of the building began to understand more about building improvement and solutions of the problems”;

“Some residents are happy that other residents are doing something, while some residents have become more engaged themselves”;

“People are taking a more amiable and active involvement in the refurbishment, subbotniks and other matters of building management”.

The relatively high level of negative changes was specified in (1) social capital, (2) fee (monthly contributions) collection, and (3) unit owners’ active participation. The second factor in the comparison with Figure VI-16 (“Reluctance to Pay”) suggests the idea that the HOAs more often face with free-riding, compared to LLCs. Most likely, the reason is the lack of the leverage on the defaulters. It is also likely that unit owners are more responsible with respect to the bills sent by the LLCs,

as some people still believe that the latter are public organizations, as described in the previous chapter.

6.5 SUMMARY

The results of the survey confirmed that the state of the common property of multifamily buildings is problematic. The most important parts of the common property: the roof, exterior walls and pipes, are in the worst condition. Only two of the 56 respondents reported a “very good state” of all parts of the common property indicated in the questionnaire. However, in either “(very) good” or a “(very) bad” state, the majority of respondents see the cause in the attitude of unit owners. In the case of bad state, buildings’ leaders often blame the irresponsibility of the owners. While in the case of a good state, leaders thank the active participation of the owners. Generally, building leaders are aware that all depends on unit owners themselves.

The survey helped to clarify the effectiveness of various forms of building management: LLC, cooperative and HOA⁵⁰. Most of the LLCs already shown to be ineffective as building managers. Cooperatives are typically established for the construction of housing and remain to manage the building after the completion of construction. According to the survey, virtually the only management method that is appropriate in the current situation, i.e., able to rally a large number of unit owners in the same building, and formed specifically for the building management, is an HOA. The facts speaking in favor of the HOA, confirmed the opinion of the experts and the assumption of the author about the need to form an HOA in each multifamily building.

The analysis of the survey revealed that the most serious problems, faced by the HOAs, associate with the attitude of unit owners (including buildings leaders) to bear their responsibilities. The most common problem is a free-riding, which,

⁵⁰ As noted earlier, a house committee is not a building management method, as its responsibilities do not include this function.

according to the survey, most often forms a negative attitude to the formation of an HOA, as well as hampers its activities.

The survey showed that the grant support is not an effective incentive for the formation of the HOA. In contrast, non-financial incentives have proven effective. According building leaders, the government minimized the obstacles to the registration of an HOA. The next step of the government might be minimizing difficulties in the activities of the HOAs, creating favorable conditions for the development of their independent operation.

The study of the perception of building leaders clarified the role of each stakeholder, including unit owners, housing maintenance companies and the government. The next chapter summarizes all findings and proposals.

VII. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

“Development issues are complicated; in many ways developing countries present far greater difficulties than more developed countries. This is because in developing nations, markets are often absent, and when present, often work imperfectly. Informational problems abound, and cultural mores may significantly affect economic behavior”

Stiglitz (2002), p. 34

7.1 CONCLUSION

7.1.1 THE FACTORS LED TO THE HOUSING MANAGEMENT CRISIS

The roots of the problem of housing management, explored in this study, lies in the past. In the Kyrgyz Republic, for more than half a century multifamily housing stock was owned by the powerful and caring Soviet state. The housing sector was heavily subsidized. The government not only owned, but also maintained its property, although the activities of public maintenance organizations (*JEKs*) created a lot of criticism. This system instigated the Soviet citizens’ perception of common spaces as the “no one’s” property and the careless attitude that firmly solidified in their minds. All this resulted in the poor condition of the common spaces and engineering of multifamily buildings.

With the collapse of the Soviet Union in 1991, the old system was bound to disappear. The Kyrgyz Republic’s central government decided to transfer the housing ownership to the sitting tenants. The latter became able to privatize rented apartments for a nominal sum, and the vast majority of the tenants took advantage of this opportunity within several years. However, the fate of the common spaces and, therefore, the responsibility for its maintenance had not been determined simultaneously with the privatization of apartments. The state continued to maintain

common property of multifamily buildings through public *JEKs*. As for the latter-day unit owners, nothing has changed with regard to the maintenance of the common property: unit owners continued to pay a small amount and to take no part in the decision-making process. The Soviet system of housing management was persisted for about a decade since the beginning of the privatization of housing.

Since the maintenance of multifamily buildings was a heavy burden for the shoestring state budget, in the late 1990s the government made the decision to demonopolize this sector. Another aim of demonopolization was the development of this sector and improvement of the management of multifamily buildings. However, the reforms had the opposite effect. In the issue, no one cared about the common property - neither the state nor the former *JEKs* or unit owners. The state was no longer the owner of the multifamily buildings. The former *JEKs* as private organizations were concerned about own profits only: the quality of their services, monitored by nobody, has declined considerably. In turn, unit owners had not realized or did not want to realize their responsibilities. The situation was aggravated by recession lasted for more than 10 years after gaining independence. The government could not allocate the budget on the previous size for the housing maintenance. In turn, many of the apartment owners, due to the rapidly increasing poverty and unemployment, had to be concerned about even more pressing issues, sometimes related to survival.

Even under such circumstances, it is obvious that a party responsible for the common property is its co-owners, i.e., unit owners. Why did unit owners not become aware of their responsibilities? Taking responsibility for something requires an understanding of the reasons of the responsibility; in this case the fact that unit owners, but not the government, are the co-owners of the common property.

To this end, in 1997 the law on HOAs was passed. Under this law, the homeowners could form an association (HOA) in order to manage their common

property. The law established a mechanism of multifamily building management. Nevertheless, the law was passed with a delay of six years. Furthermore, the law was characterized by incompleteness and, consequently, it did not work adequately. As a rule, the responsibility for anything is set by strict rules, with the definition of liability for the non-compliance. However, the institute of HOAs, introduced by this law, was voluntary. Placing the responsibility on a voluntary basis could not have positive results.

The absence of an effective mechanism of multifamily building management has led to an almost total lack of care for common spaces. Currently it is the main problem of multifamily housing of the Kyrgyz Republic. The deterioration of multifamily housing stock can lead to the serious consequences. Because of the failure to conduct timely routine maintenance, now many of the co-owners of the common property have to carry out its major refurbishment. Lack of timely refurbishment of the building leads to an emergency state. For 22 years since the beginning of the reforms, the condition of multifamily housing and its maintenance services, that were supposed to have been developed, on the contrary, worsened. Although the roots of this problem lie in the past, the decisions must be taken now and as soon as possible.

7.1.2 THE BEST HOUSING MANAGEMENT PRACTICES AND THE GAPS TO BE ELIMINATED

All post-socialist countries, having a similar background, in late 1980s – early 1990s began to reform their housing sector. However, the steps taken and, as a result, the effects of reforms differ from country to country, and in some ways - from region to region. Comparing the Kyrgyz Republic with Hungary, that relatively successfully introduced housing reforms, it was taken into account that the length and stiffness of the socialist regime and the subsequent rotation angle in those two states were rather different. However, analysis of Hungary's experience revealed that its success is due

to the implementation of the *complex and synchronous measures*. These decisions include (1) mandatory HOA, (2) creation of the conditions for independent operation of HOA, and (3) the training of sufficient number of housing managers, and others. No less important was the adoption of measures for the inevitability of the above requirements, such as mandatory HOA.

In the Kyrgyz Republic, *the key decisions were stretched for decades*. Some *essential decisions are still not adopted*. The main difference of the Kyrgyz housing management system from the common practice is as follows. Kyrgyz legislation does not oblige unit owners to take measures to maintain common property. As a result, many of the multifamily buildings are not maintained at all.

Some unit owners, who are aware of the consequences, are willing to bear the burden of the maintenance of common property. The survey showed that the buildings with HOA better cope with the management of common property. Expert opinions also agree on that. Nevertheless, the formation of HOA is not required. In addition, HOAs' helplessness against free-riders and the lack of housing managers complicate HOAs' activities.

The need for government regulation seems obvious, at least until the formation of a full-fledged market, where *the unit owners have the body representing their interests*, while *housing managers improve their services in a competitive environment*. We do not "release" our children in the "free floating" right after their birth, but nurture and watch them at least until their maturity. Just as a child needs to be trained the survival skills, formation of housing management market takes time and effort.

The following are recommendations for further reforms, aimed at the development and full activity of the housing management system.

7.2 RECOMMENDATIONS

The ultimate goal of the proposed reforms is to develop a mechanism of systematic maintenance of the common property. Hungarian housing reform experience is taken as the destination. Figure VII-29 shows the main tools proposed to form the full-fledged housing management market.

FIGURE VII-29: TOOLS TO PROMOTE THE FORMATION OF THE MARKET
Source: Developed by author

7.2.1 FORMATION OF HOUSING MANAGEMENT SERVICE USERS (UNIT OWNERS) MARKET

Though there are a number of different causes, the only effective solution is taking responsibility for the common property by its co-owners. To do this, decisions on the following direction should be made.

FORMATION AND MEMBERSHIP IN THE HOA

On the experience of CEE countries, experts agree that the HOA is the most suitable (if not the only) way to combine a motley community of unit owners in the former state-owned buildings. In view of the severity of the problem, the imaginary freedom in matters of the housing management should be replaced by strict but equal for all rules on the *mandatory formation of the HOA* for every multifamily building (except for the buildings with a very small number of apartments). Due to the historical, cultural and other reasons, without such requirements, the formation of the

HOAs in 100% of the buildings by other methods (e.g. encouragement and advocacy methods) is extremely unlikely.

However, the adoption of legislative requirements on mandatory HOA cannot be sufficient for its successful implementation. Even after making the formation of HOA obligatory, the passivity of unit owners and the rejection of an HOA by some leaders of buildings, revealed by the survey, would interfere with fulfilling of the requirements. The survey found that methods of persuasion, rather than financial incentives, are more effective for the formation of an HOA. Thus, the solution suggested by the draft Housing Code (following the Russian experience) to *empower the local governments* to convene a general meeting of unit owners (in the buildings that has not established an HOA up to a certain period) *with consequent formation of an HOA* by unit owners present at the meeting, seems the optimal. The *establishment of the penalties* for the owners of the units in the buildings, refusing to form an HOA, seems unavoidable.

Setting the *mandatory membership of all unit owners* in the HOA is suggested by the draft Housing Code of the Kyrgyz Republic. This is a logical decision, since the HOA is formed to manage the whole building.

After HOA is formed, its smooth functioning depends on effectiveness and efficiency, discussed below.

HOAS' EFFECTIVENESS

According to the experience of other countries, *the quorum* for decision-making in the HOA should be reduced to *a minimum*. The survey confirmed the difficulties HOAs face due to the passivity of unit owners and the consequent problems with the convening of the general meeting of the HOA.

Numerous posts on the online forums suggest that there is a problem of bad faith of HOAs' chairpersons. An effective system of *monitoring of the performance*

of the HOAs' chairpersons by the unit owners, associations of HOAs and \ or local governments should be developed. Democratic decision-making can increase the activities of unit owners and reduce the cases of usurpation of power by HOAs' leaders.

Experts say the dependence of the HOAs' efficiency and effectiveness on the number of the units in the building. As a rule, very small HOAs tend to be inefficient, but very large HOAs (combining several buildings) are more likely to be ineffective. There are examples of some of the countries in transition, where homeowners associations combine several dozen buildings. In such cases, the quality of their work may be similar to the activities of the Soviet *JEKs*. It is expedient to establish a minimum and a maximum number of apartments in the HOA, e.g. a minimum of 7 apartments for an HOA consisting of one building, and a maximum of 60 apartments for an HOA combining several buildings located next to each other.

The *regular information and legal support of the HOAs' chairpersons* can raise their professionalism. According to the Bishkek Development Agency, the chairpersons of the HOA actively participate in ongoing training. During the survey, the chairpersons of the HOAs pointed to the need for more training. Establishing the department responsible for conducting training and consultations for the chairpersons of HOAs on a regular basis in each executive body of local governments can resolve this issue.

FINANCIAL STABILITY OF HOA

An HOA has some financial benefits as a legal person. It is entitled to receive grants for the refurbishment of the common property. An HOA is supposed to have a bank account where the funds to take timely measures to maintain the common property can be accumulated. It is obvious that the main and permanent source of the HOA's funds is the monthly contributions of its members. In the absence of the

system of debt collection and a virtual lack of access to loans its resources are limited, which explains the weakness of many HOAs.

EMPOWERMENT LEVERAGE OVER DEBTORS

The unwillingness to pay is, according to the building leaders surveyed, one of major obstacles in the management of the building. The owners who refuse to pay the monthly contributions for the maintenance of the common property should “get what they pay for”. However, as the common property has the features of the common pool resource, it is extremely difficult to limit its use by the debtors. Given a lack of effective ways of debt collection, conscientious co-owners have to pay for the debtors. *Empowering the HOAs with the leverage over the debtors* is the best solution to the problem. The method of its fulfillment provided in the draft Housing Code on the conferring the administrative commissions of the local governments (less bureaucratic than the proceedings in the courts) the authority to hear cases of the non-payment of financial contributions seems most convenient. Imposition of a lien on personal property of the defaulter can be an alternative or an additional solution. The leverage on free-riders should be given not only to HOAs, but also to cooperatives, as the survey revealed difficulties the latter face with contribution collection.

FACILITATION OF ACCESS TO BANK LOANS

Major refurbishment of the common property is very costly, especially in the current economic and social realities of the Kyrgyz Republic. Bank loans can be an essential source of funds. Due to the low turnout at the general meetings, the establishment of a *minimum quorum for a voting on obtaining a bank loan* can reduce bureaucratic obstacles within the HOA.

However, according to the survey, the chairpersons are skeptical of bank loans, perhaps because of the high interest rates, common in the Kyrgyz banks. *Tax reduction for the loans for the HOAs* and other mechanisms creating favorable conditions can help the development of this practice.

STATUTORY RESERVE FUND

The purpose of the reserve fund of an HOA is the accumulation of funds for the timely overhaul of the common property. At the same time, the difficulties in the collection of large contributions in case of emergency, which are inevitable in the present state of the common property, should also be considered. With this in mind, *the reserve fund should be mandatory for each HOA.*

FINANCIAL CONDITION OF UNIT OWNERS AS AN INDEPENDENT FACTOR INFLUENCING THE PROGRESS OF REFORM

Carrying the burden of expenses for maintenance of the common property has been hampered in the 1990s because of the deep economic crisis. In the next decade, the situation began to improve. According to the World Bank, in the last decade the level of poverty in the Kyrgyz Republic has decreased (see Figure II-5), which in turn should result in an increased demand for higher quality goods and services. Sustainable growth in real estate prices can also indirectly indicate income growth (Figure VII-30).

FIGURE VII-30: PRICE PER SQUARE METER OF APARTMENT IN BISHKEK
Source: Gosregister, cited by online news agency “Akipress”, 2013 (composed by author)

Social heterogeneity of unit owners in the same building raised in Chapter II as a factor, preventing the unification of owners as a single customer, is continuously flattening nowadays. For more than 20 years (since the start of privatization and thus

gaining by citizens the right to buy and sell their apartments), there is a gradual stratification of society by type and location of housing. Wealthier citizens are moving to buildings located in the city centers and other prestigious areas and/or built in the 1980s and later (including “*elitniy*” buildings⁵¹), which are in a relatively better condition and thus more expensive. In turn, the citizens whose financial situation over the last 20 years has worsened, are forced to move to a less comfortable accommodation, built in 1960-70s and earlier, or located on the city outskirts, which are cheaper by 1.5-2 times and often the most deteriorated. Such unit owners usually cannot afford common property’s major refurbishment, therefore those buildings are most in need of financial support from outside.

HOAS AND THE LOCAL GOVERNMENTS

Bishkek local governments carry out active work in the support of multifamily buildings, including the provision of subsidies to needy unit owners, the provision of grants to the HOAs, and the holding of seminars for HOAs’ leaders. Some other local governments are also carrying out supporting activities (however, the subsidized local governments are more limited in their activities due to scarce resources).

Nevertheless, these efforts cannot be enough to solve existing problems. The necessary legislative provisions can be taken only at the national level. In this case, the activities of the local governments to support HOAs can be enhanced due to the anticipated increase in the number of HOAs. Due to the limited capacity of the local governments, the prioritization of grant support of the HOAs with a large number of needy owners is desirable. The local governments could continue to promote HOAs’ vigorous activity, because the existence of dormant HOAs is still open to question.

⁵¹ *Elitniy dom* (literally “elite house”, colloq. “*elitka*”) – high-class multifamily buildings located in prime locations, with a larger area rooms and enhanced security, etc.

RAISING AWARENESS OF THE OWNERS OF THEIR RIGHTS AND RESPONSIBILITIES

There are still believes among unit owners that all that lies behind the walls of their apartments is not their concern. There is a need to clarify to unit owners about changes that took place during two decades, about their responsibility for the common property, inextricably linked with the rights to the apartments. This can be achieved through a complex of instruments.

State registration of the share of each unit owner in the common property and recording this information in certificates of titles to each unit can be an effective method of influencing a widespread lack of recognizing rights and responsibilities for the common property. The *outreach* by the HOAs' chairpersons together with the local governments also plays an important role. At the same time, for the widespread dissemination of information, *long and massive information campaign on the national level* seems necessary. Outreach should include explanations that the investments in the common property increase the attractiveness (financial and aesthetic) and the safety of owners' homes. Another important tool is the *inspection of the state of the common property* and bringing the inspection results to unit owners with an explanation of implications for the given building and setting penalties for the violations found.

Because building management service users are a large number of ordinary citizens, formation of their market will require considerable effort. On the contrary, the formation of service providers market may be less complicated.

7.2.2 FORMATION OF HOUSING MANAGEMENT SERVICE PROVIDERS (HOUSING MANAGERS) MARKET

TRAINING OF PROFESSIONAL MANAGERS AND HOAS' LEADERS

The survey showed that some leaders do an excellent job with their responsibilities, smoothly managing common property and unit owners. Such buildings are in better state, while unit owners are in a favorable position.

However, there are still many multifamily buildings not maintained at all or run by the LLCs. Regarding the latter, the quality of their services, according to the survey, has declined (most likely due to a lack of a competitive market). Although the cost of their services is growing, their activities are reducing. In recent years, awareness of unit owners is rising, and some of them are refusing the services of the unscrupulous LLCs. It is a logical decision, but does not solve the problem of a lack of maintenance of the buildings.

After the formation of the HOAs, its leaders are faced with a problem of lack of managerial skills. *Training for leaders of cooperatives and HOAs* can partly solve the problem. Some leaders, having received the necessary skills, will be able to manage common property independently.

However, the existence of a unit owner suitable for the post of HOA chairperson in each multifamily building is unlikely. For such buildings, in order to avoid “one-sided” reforms and to create a market balance, the *training of the sufficient number of housing managers* is necessary. The experience of some CEE countries (where this work is carried out over a long period) can be used: training can be provided by the independent non-government organizations such as educational institutions and/or associations of HOAs. When training managers, the types of buildings, common in the Kyrgyz Republic, and their features should be taken into account.

Nevertheless, the experience of other countries shows that the screening of unscrupulous managers takes time. Most of the serious violations of managing companies in Russia are related to the excessive rates and the misuse and misappropriation of funds of unit owners. *The role of a manager should be limited to the management of common property. The collection and pooling of funds should be carried out by an HOA.* The leaders of HOAs are co-owners of the common property and live in the given buildings. Thus, they have a direct interest in its preservation, therefore serious financial mismanagement on their part is less likely than on the part of managers.

INCREASING THE ATTRACTIVENESS OF THE SERVICE SUPPLIERS' MARKET

The *increasing number of HOAs*, giving rise to increased demand for the services of housing managers, should become a basic factor in increasing the attractiveness of the housing management service suppliers' market. At the same time, common tools to improve the attractiveness of the market as *tax breaks* need to be enforced. Probably, until the formation of the market, *government regulation of the amount of payment for management services* will be required.

It is now obvious that the problem of lack of maintenance of the common property of multifamily buildings will not be solved by itself. The proposed reforms should be carried out by the central government with the distribution of functions to local government and non-government organizations.

7.3 LIMITATIONS AND SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER STUDIES

In this research, the opinions of buildings' leaders were collected through a survey. The perception of ordinary unit owners, expressed in the online forums, was also studied. Further studies could capture existing concerns directly from unit owners. In addition, it is worth to hear the opinion of the former *JEKs* (LLCs).

Due to language limitations, learning from the CEE states was not deep enough. For further research, it would be useful to study CEE experience in training of individual housing managers.

The research of the market of the HOA's employees (accountants, plumbers, welders, cleaners, etc.), necessary for the activities of the HOAs, can also deepen the knowledge on the housing management sector.

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"On social support of Bishkek residents poor and entitled to benefits for housing", regulation of the Bishkek City Kenesh (<i>Постановление Бишкекского городского кенеша "О</i>	

<i>социальной поддержке малоимущих и имеющих право на льготы жителей города Бишкек"), 2012.....</i>	<i>66</i>
"On state registration of rights to real property and transactions with it", law of the Kyrgyz Republic (<i>Закон Кыргызской Республики "О государственной регистрации прав на недвижимое имущество и сделок с ним"</i>), 1998	<i>57</i>
"On strengthening the role of house committees in the management of the public housing stock", resolution of the Council of Ministers of the RSFSR (<i>Постановление Совета Министров РСФСР "Об усилении роли домовых комитетов в управлении государственным жилищным фондом"</i>), 1968	<i>14</i>
"On the concept of the reform of housing and communal services in the Kyrgyz Republic", resolution of the central government of the Kyrgyz Republic (<i>Постановление Правительства Кыргызской Республики «"О концепции реформы жилищно-коммунального хозяйства в Кыргызской Республике"</i>), 1998.....	<i>19</i>
"On the development of housing construction in the USSR", resolution of the the Central Committee of the Communist Party and the Council of Ministers of the USSR (<i>Постановление ЦК КПСС и Совета Министров СССР "О развитии жилищного строительства в СССР"</i>), 1957	<i>7</i>
"On the establishment of housing refurbishment enterprise "Bishkekjlremont", regulation of the Bishkek City Kenesh (<i>Постановление мэрии города Бишкек "О создании жилищно-ремонтного предприятия «Бишкекжилремонт»"</i>), 1997	<i>18</i>
"On the development of precast concrete structures and components for construction", resolution of the the Central Committee of the Communist Party and the Council of Ministers of the USSR (<i>Постановление ЦК КПСС и Совета Министров СССР "О развитии производства сборных железобетонных конструкций и деталей для строительства"</i>), 1954	<i>7</i>
"On the implementation of the Law "On privatization of housing in the Republic of Kyrgyzstan", resolution of the Supreme Council of the Republic of Kyrgyzstan (<i>Постановление Верховного Совета Республики Кыргызстан "О введении в действие Закона Республики Кыргызстан "О приватизации жилищного фонда в Республике Кыргызстан"</i>), 1991.....	<i>18</i>
Civil Code of the Kyrgyz Republic, part I (<i>"Гражданский Кодекс Кыргызской Республики"</i>), 1996	<i>20, 49</i>
Housing Code of the Russian Federation (<i>"Жилищный Кодекс Российской Федерации"</i>), 2004	<i>26</i>

The draft Housing Code of the Kyrgyz Republic (*Проект Жилищного Кодекса Кыргызской Республики*) Available on http://www.kenesh.kg/RU/Articles/3212-Proekt_ZHilishhnogo_kodeksa_KR (in Russian)..... 61

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A: INCENTIVE GRANTS PROGRAM IMPLEMENTATION

(Source: City Development Agency report (2012), composed by author)

Пожалуйста, обращайтесь по следующим контактными данным в случае возникновения вопросов и предложений: электронный адрес gulnarakoeva@gmail.com, номер телефона в Японии (081)80-4616-1011.

1. Местонахождение многоквартирного дома (пожалуйста выберите 1 подходящий ответ)
 - a) Первомайский район
 - b) Ленинский район
 - c) Октябрьский район
 - d) Свердловский район
2. Год постройки дома: 19_____ год.
3. Серия многоквартирного дома (пожалуйста выберите 1 подходящий ответ)
 - a) “Сталинка”
 - b) “Хрущевка”
 - c) “Индивидуалка”
 - d) 104 серии
 - e) 105 серии
 - f) 106 серии
 - g) Другое (пожалуйста уточните серию дома) _____
4. Сколько помещений находится в многоквартирном доме?
Всего помещений _____ (включая жилых _____, нежилых _____).
5. Первоначальная принадлежность многоквартирного дома (пожалуйста выберите 1 подходящий ответ)
 - a) государственный
 - b) ведомственный
 - c) кооперативный
 - d) другое (пожалуйста уточните) _____
6. Форма управления домом в настоящее время (пожалуйста выберите 1 подходящий ответ)
 - a) домовый комитет
 - b) жилищный кооператив
 - c) ТСЖ
 - d) ОсОО
 - e) другое (пожалуйста уточните) _____
7. Данная форма управления домом создана в _____ году.
8. Каковы причины выбора и создания данной формы управления?

9. Достоинства и недостатки данной формы управления

Достоинства _____

Недостатки _____

10. Пожалуйста обведите ту цифру которая наилучшим образом отражает степень значительности нижеперечисленных проблем при управлении многоквартирным домом

	Крайне незначительная проблема	Незначительная проблема	Значительная проблема	Крайне значительная проблема
a) Созыв общего собрания жителей	1	2	3	4
b) Выборы председателя домкома\кооператива\ТСЖ	1	2	3	4
c) Низкий уровень ежемесячных взносов за обслуживание, уборку, и т.д.	1	2	3	4
d) Нежелание жителей оплачивать сборы за обслуживание, уборку и т.д.	1	2	3	4
e) Состояние общего имущества дома	1	2	3	4
f) другое (пожалуйста уточните) _____	1	2	3	4

11. Пожалуйста обведите ту цифру которая наилучшим образом отражает степень пассивности\активности участия нижеперечисленных граждан и организаций в управлении вашим многоквартирным домом

	Очень пассивное участие	Пассивное участие	Активное участие	Очень активное участие
a) Руководитель дома (Вы)	1	2	3	4
b) ОсОО управляющее домом	1	2	3	4
c) Жители дома	1	2	3	4
d) Другое (пожалуйста уточните) _____	1	2	3	4

12. Размер ежемесячных взносов за управление, уборку и т.д. дома составляет _____ сом за кв. м. помещения

13. Пожалуйста обведите ту цифру которая наилучшим образом отражает Ваше мнение относительно повышения ежемесячных взносов за управление, уборку и т.д.

Убедительно против повышения	Против повышения	За повышение	Убедительно за повышение
1	2	3	4

Пожалуйста уточните причины _____

14. Если за повышение, то на сколько считаете нужным повысить взносы?
на _____%.

15. Сколько собственников помещений не оплачивают ежемесячные взносы на управление, уборку и т.д.?
_____ квартир (включая государственных _____, частных _____)
_____ нежилых помещений (включая государственных _____, частных _____)

16. Пожалуйста обведите ту цифру которая наилучшим образом отражает причины неоплаты ежемесячных взносов за обслуживание, уборку и т.д.

	Очень редкая причина	Редкая причина	Частая причина	Очень частая причина
a) Отсутствие денег (бедность)	1	2	3	4
b) Нежелание платить взносы	1	2	3	4
c) Неизвестность местонахождения собственника	1	2	3	4
d) Другое (пожалуйста уточните причину) _____	1	2	3	4

17. Пожалуйста обведите ту цифру которая наилучшим образом отражает состояние общего имущества вашего многоквартирного дома

	Очень плохое	Плохое	Хорошее	Очень хорошее
a) Крыша	1	2	3	4
b) Подъезд	1	2	3	4
c) Трубопроводы (канализация, водопровод)	1	2	3	4
d) Наружные стены многоквартирного дома	1	2	3	4
e) Уличное освещение	1	2	3	4
f) Двор	1	2	3	4
g) Другое (пожалуйста уточните) _____	1	2	3	4

18. Пожалуйста укажите причины данного состояния общего имущества дома

19. Пожалуйста обведите ту цифру которая наилучшим образом отражает Ваше мнение относительно создания ТСЖ в многоквартирных домах

Убедительно	Против создания	За создание ТСЖ	Убедительно за
-------------	-----------------	-----------------	----------------

против создания ТСЖ	ТСЖ		создание ТСЖ
1	2	3	4

20. Пожалуйста укажите причины _____

21. Пожалуйста обведите ту цифру которая наилучшим образом отражает причины нежелания некоторых жителей создавать ТСЖ

	Очень редкая причина	Редкая причина	Частая причина	Очень частая причина
a) Низкая инициативность жителей	1	2	3	4
b) Барьеры со стороны государства (правовые, бюрократические, др.)	1	2	3	4
c) <u>Нежелание</u> жителей брать на себя ответственность за содержание общего имущества многоквартирного дома	1	2	3	4
d) <u>Неготовность</u> жителей брать на себя ответственность за содержание общего имущества многоквартирного дома	1	2	3	4
e) Создание ТСЖ не выгодно для жителей (пожалуйста уточните в чем не выгодно) _____	1	2	3	4
f) Другое (пожалуйста уточните причины) _____ _____	1	2	3	4

22. Пожалуйста обведите ту цифру которая наилучшим образом отражает вероятную эффективность нижеперечисленных мер для увеличения количества создаваемых ТСЖ

	Очень не эффективно	Не эффективно	Эффективно	Очень эффективно
a) Разъяснительная работа среди населения	1	2	3	4
b) Законодательное обязательное всех многоквартирных домов создать ТСЖ	1	2	3	4
c) Усиление полномочий ТСЖ	1	2	3	4
d) Безвозмездная финансовая помощь ТСЖ	1	2	3	4

(гранты)				
e) Упрощение выдачи банковских кредитов для ТСЖ	1	2	3	4
f) Другое (пожалуйста уточните) _____	1	2	3	4

23. Пожалуйста обведите ту цифру которая наилучшим образом отражает нуждаемость ТСЖ в нижеперечисленных видах поддержки

	Не нужно	нужно	Очень нужно
a) Усиление полномочий ТСЖ	1	2	3
b) Безвозмездная финансовая помощь ТСЖ (гранты)	1	2	3
c) Упрощение выдачи банковских кредитов для ТСЖ	1	2	3
d) Обучение персонала ТСЖ	1	2	3
e) Другое (пожалуйста уточните) _____	1	2	3

24. Известно ли Вам о Программе Стимулирующих Грантов г. Бишкек? (пожалуйста выберите 1 подходящий ответ)

1. не известно
2. известно но не принимал(а) участие
3. подавал(а) заявку на получение стимулирующего гранта но не прошла конкурс и не получил(а) грант
4. подавал(а) заявку на получение стимулирующего гранта и получил(а) грант в 20____ году на ремонт _____.

Следующие 4 вопроса адресованы руководителям многоквартирных домов обслуживались или обслуживаются ОсОО (бывшими домоуправлениями)

25. В какие годы ваш многоквартирный дом обслуживался ОсОО (бывшим домоуправлением)?
с 19____ года по _____ год

26. Обслуживается ли ваш дом ОсОО (бывшим домоуправлением) в настоящее время? (пожалуйста выберите 1 подходящий ответ)

- Да, в настоящее время обслуживается
 - Нет, мы расторгнули договор с ОсОО и в настоящее время самостоятельно управляем многоквартирным домом
- Пожалуйста уточните причины _____

27. Пожалуйста обведите ту цифру которая наилучшим образом отражает уровень качества обслуживания ОсОО вашего дома

Очень низкий	Низкий	Высокий	Очень высокий
1	2	3	4

28. Пожалуйста укажите причины Вашей оценки

Следующие 3 вопроса адресованы председателю ТСЖ			
29. Пожалуйста обведите ту цифру которая наилучшим образом отражает уровень трудностей с которыми вы столкнулись при создании ТСЖ			
	Очень трудно	Трудно	Легко
a) Созыв общего собрания жителей и сбор их подписей	1	2	3
b) Регистрация ТСЖ в органах юстиции	1	2	3
c) Другое (пожалуйста уточните) _____	1	2	3
30. Какие изменения произошли в вашем доме после создания ТСЖ?			
	Значительно ухудшилось	Ухудшилось	Улучшилось
a) Состояние общего имущества дома	1	2	3
b) Собираемость взносов за обслуживание дома	1	2	3
c) Отношение жителей к общему имуществу дома	1	2	3
d) Активность жителей в управлении домом	1	2	3
e) Взаимоотношения жителей между собой	1	2	3
f) Другое (пожалуйста уточните) _____	1	2	3
31. Пожалуйста поясните _____			

32. Ваш возраст (пожалуйста обведите)
 a) 20-30 лет b) 31-40 лет c) 41-50 лет d) 51-60 лет e) 61-70 лет f) 71-80 лет

33. Пол

- Женский
- Мужской

34. Пожалуйста укажите Ваше предыдущее место работы и должность

35. Опыт работы в качестве руководителя многоквартирного дома

с _____ года.

*Благодарим Вас за уделенное время и внимание.
Ваш вклад в нашу работу очень ценен для нас. Если Вы желаете получить краткое резюме основных результатов, пожалуйста, напишите разборчиво Ваши имя и адрес.*

ФИО _____

Номер телефона _____

Электронный адрес _____

Адрес:

г. Бишкек, улица _____, дом _____, квартира _____

Название ТСЖ или кооператива (если есть) _____

Хотели бы Вы сообщить что-то еще о том, что Вы думаете о вопросе содержания многоквартирных домов? Если да, пожалуйста, используйте место на этой странице. Также, просим Вас изложить любые замечания и предложения по усовершенствованию данного исследования, чтобы лучше понять, с какими проблемами сталкивается многоквартирный дом и его руководитель.

При составлении опросника использовались источники:

<http://diesel.elcat.kg/index.php?showtopic=1246936> (карта г. Бишкек)

А.А. Сусоколов, Технология социологического исследования, 2007 (дизайн опросника)

ENGLISH VERSION

QUESTIONNAIRE

Management of Multifamily Buildings.

House Committees, HOAs and Housing Cooperatives' Chairpersons' Attitude Survey

Dear resident of Bishkek,

This questionnaire was prepared by a student of Meiji University (Japan) Kokoeva Gulnara, who is studying under the Japan International Cooperation Centre program, aimed to strengthen the capacity of state and municipal employees of the Kyrgyz Republic.

The purpose of the questionnaire is to examine the views of chairpersons of multi-family buildings for writing master thesis on the content of the common property buildings in Bishkek. The study seeks to take action to support the condition of multi-family buildings and improve the interaction between the chairpersons of houses and government agencies / local authorities.

You do not need to write down your name when filling out the questionnaire. All your answers will be anonymous and taken into account when summarizing survey.

At your request, you will be informed about results of survey in order for you to find answers of other interviewed chairpersons.

We realize that you are busy and your time is valuable. However, we hope that the 15 minutes it takes to complete this questionnaire will help in improving the condition of multi-family buildings in our city and in the activities of the people leading these houses. We appreciate your cooperation.

Please feel free to contact us: email address gulnarakokoeva@gmail.com, telephone number in Japan (081)80-4616-1011.

1. Location of the multi-family building (please select one applicable answer)
 - a) Pervomayskiy district
 - b) Leninskiy district
 - c) Oktyabr'skiy district
 - d) Sverdlovskiy district

2. Year when building was built: 19_____ year.

3. The multi-family building's type (please select one applicable answer)
 - a) "Stalinka"
 - b) "Chrushyovka"
 - c) "Individualka"
 - d) 104 series
 - e) 105 series
 - f) 106 series

4. How many premises are in the multi-family building?
all premises _____ (including residential _____, non-residential _____).

5. The initial belonging of the house (please select one applicable answer)
 - a) public
 - b) departmental (public corporation)
 - c) cooperative
 - d) other (please specify) _____

6. The form of the building management nowadays (please select one applicable answer)
 - a) house committee
 - b) cooperative
 - c) HOA
 - d) LLC (not managed)
 - e) other (please specify) _____

7. This form of building management was established in _____ year.

8. What are the reasons for the creation of this form of management?

9. What are the advantages and disadvantages of this form of management
Advantages

Disadvantages

10. Please circle the number that most reflects the seriousness of challenges your multifamily building is facing

	Very minor challenge	Minor challenge	Main challenge	Very main challenge
a) Election of the chairman of the House Committee/HOA	1	2	3	4
b) Low level of monthly payments for the management, cleaning, etc.	1	2	3	4
c) Refusal of some residents to pay fees for management, cleaning, etc.	1	2	3	4
d) Refurbishment of the common property of the building	1	2	3	4
e) Other (please specify issue) _____	1	2	3	4

11. Please circle the number that best reflects the level of involvement of the following individuals and organizations in management of the building

	Very low involvement	Low involvement	High involvement	Very high involvement
a) Head of the organization (you)	1	2	3	4
b) Multifamily buildings' maintenance Ltd	1	2	3	4
c) Residents of a multifamily building	1	2	3	4
d) Other (please specify who) _____	1	2	3	4

12. What is the amount of monthly fees for management, cleaning, operation and maintenance, etc. of the building?
 _____KGS per square meter of housing

13. Please circle the number that best reflects your opinion on raising \ unraising monthly fees for management, cleaning, operation and maintenance, etc.

Strongly against increasing	Against increasing	Agree with increasing	Strongly agree with increasing
1	2	3	4

Please state why _____

14. If agree, in your opinion the fee should increase to _____%.

15. How many owners of the premises in your building refuse to pay monthly fees for management, cleaning, operation and maintenance, etc.?

_____ residential premises (including public _____, private _____)
 _____ non-residential premises (including public _____, private _____)

16. Please circle the number that most reflects the reason of non-payment of monthly fees

	Very minor reason	Minor reason	Main reason	Very main reason
a) Lack of money (poverty)	1	2	3	4
b) Unwillingness to pay fees	1	2	3	4
c) Location of the owner is unknown	1	2	3	4
d) Other (please specify issue) _____	1	2	3	4

17. Please circle the number that most reflects the condition of the common property of the building (entrance, roof, etc.)

	Very bad	Bad	Good	Very good
a) Roof	1	2	3	4
b) Entrance	1	2	3	4
c) Stairs	1	2	3	4
d) Street lightning	1	2	3	4
e) Courtyard	1	2	3	4
f) Other (please specify) _____	1	2	3	4

18. Please specify the reason of the current state of the building's common property

19. Please circle the number that best reflects your views on the creation \ not creation of HOA in multi-family buildings

Strongly against creation of HOA	Against creation of HOA	Agree with creation of HOA	Strongly agree with creation of HOA
1	2	3	4

20. Please indicate the reasons for your opinion _____

21. Please circle the number that best reflects the reason for which in some buildings HOAs are not created

	Very minor reason	Minor reason	Main reason	Very main reason
a) Low initiative of residents	1	2	3	4
b) Barriers from the government (legislative, bureaucratic, etc.)	1	2	3	4
c) Unwillingness of people to take responsibility for the common property of a multi-family building	1	2	3	4
d) Creation of HOA is not favorable for the residents (please specify why) _____ _____	1	2	3	4
e) Other (please specify issue) _____ _____	1	2	3	4

22. In your opinion, what measures should be taken to increase the number of created HOAs?

23. Please circle the number that best reflects the level of HOAs needs in local authorities \ state agencies support

	Very minor need	Minor need	Main need	Very main need
a) Strengthen the powers of HOAs	1	2	3	4
b) Funding support	1	2	3	4
c) Training of personnel HOA	1	2	3	4
d) Other (please specify) _____	1	2	3	4

24. Do you know about the Bishkek Incentive Grants program? (please select one applicable answer)

- No
- I know, but I have not taken participation yet
- I have filed an application for Incentive Grants but did not pass competition and receive a grant
- I have received Incentive Grant in 20____ year for refurbishment of _____

The next 4 questions are for the heads of multi-family buildings that used to hire or current private companies (former “domoupravleniye”) to maintain common property of a building

25. In what year your multi-family building was maintained by private Ltd Company (former “domoupravleniye”)?
from 19 ____ year to ____ year

26. Is your multifamily building currently maintained by Ltd private company (former “domoupravleniye”)?

- o Yes, it is currently maintained
- o No, we terminated the contract with the Ltd, and currently multi-family building is maintained by residents themselves

Please specify the reason _____

27. Please circle the number that best reflects level of quality of activities of the Ltd private company maintaining your building

Very low quality	Low quality	High quality	Very high quality
1	2	3	4

28. Please state the reasons for your assessment _____

*The next three questions are addressed to the heads of multi-family buildings that **already have in HOAs***

29. Please circle the number that best reflects level of difficulties encountered in establishing HOA

	Very difficult	Difficult	Easy
a) Convocation of General meeting of the inhabitants of the house, the collection of their signatures	1	2	3
b) HOA registration with the justice authorities	1	2	3
c) Other (please specify) _____	1	2	3

30. How did the state of the common property of the house change after creation of HOA

	Very negatively	Negatively	Positively
a) The state of the common property	1	2	3
b) Collection of monthly contributions	1	2	3
c) The attitude of the residents to the common property	1	2	3

d) Participation of the residents in the building management	1	2	3	4
e) Social capital	1	2	3	4
f) Other (please specify) _____	1	2	3	4

31. Please specify what exactly has changed _____

32. Year of your birth 19_____ year

33. Your gender (please circle)

- Female
- Male

34. Please specify your former place of employment and position _____

35. Your working experience as head of the multi-family building since _____ year.

*Thank you for your time and consideration.
 Would you like to say something more about what you think of the maintenance of the multi-family buildings? If so, please use the space on this page. Also, please provide any comments and suggestions for improvement of this study to better understand the challenges facing the multi-family buildings and its leader.
 Your contribution to our work is very valuable for us. If you want to get a brief summary of the main results, please clearly write your name and address*

Your name _____

Telephone number _____

Email address _____

The multi-family building's address:

Bishkek, _____ district, _____ street, building N _____

Sources: Sukosolov A.A., Sociological Research Technology, 2007 (questionnaire design)
<http://diesel.elcat.kg/index.php?showtopic=1246936> (map of the Bishkek)